

Technische
Universität
Braunschweig

Study Thesis No. 827

Model-based Reinforcement Learning for Accelerated Learning From CFD Simulations

Jan Erik Schulze

Issued by: Prof. Dr.-Ing. R. Radespiel
Institut für Strömungsmechanik
Head of Institute: Prof. Dr.-Ing. R. Radespiel
Technische Universität Braunschweig

Supervisor: Dr.-Ing. A. Weiner, (TU Braunschweig)

Publication: 02. March 2022

Acknowledgement

First of all I want to thank my supervisor Andre Weiner for giving me the opportunity to conduct this project. His support and supervision throughout the course of this thesis have always been excellent and his advice has always been helpful.

Furthermore, I want to thank all people who supported me throughout the course of this thesis, especially my roommate and friend Janik Brzosa, for always being there during coffee breaks and having an open ear.

Finally I want to thank my girlfriend Jenny for always putting up with me, never giving up on me and giving me hope, when in doubt. You are the best.

Abstract

This thesis presents and evaluates an approach for model-based deep reinforcement learning used for active flow control of a 2D flow past a cylinder to accelerate the learning process of the DRL agent. In the wake of a 2D flow past a cylinder, a von Kármán vortex street can be observed. By rotating the cylinder a DRL agent tries to find a proper control law for mitigating the vorticity and therefore the drag and the oscillations of the drag and the lift at the cylinder. Since the DRL agent only has access to 400 fixed pressure sensors on the cylinder's surface a feed-forward neural network is developed for predicting the pressure values of the next state using the pressure from the previous states and the action taken by the agent. The environment model is used autoregressively to predict whole trajectories from only one start state. The presented approach shows the general feasibility of model-based trajectory sampling for active flow control using DRL. Furthermore, the influence of the number of subsequent previous states used for the prediction of the next state is investigated, showing that more subsequent states yield a better prediction accuracy. Also, the reduction of the number of pressure sensors used for the environment model input is investigated considering the memory consumption and prediction accuracy. The resulting model predicts the next state containing 400 pressure values, as well as the drag and lift coefficient from 30 subsequent time steps containing only 16 pressure values plus the action. The influence of the number of neurons per hidden layer has also been examined, revealing that the prediction accuracy rises with a rising number of neurons per hidden layer but the models have not been able to provide a stable and promising DRL training. Although the tested neural network architectures are not sufficient enough for conducting a working model-based DRL training run, this thesis reveals several pitfalls and challenges of environment modeling for this flow problem and proposes the next steps to take from here.

The code developed throughout this thesis can be accessed on github: <https://git.io/JiJPb>.

Contents

Nomenclature	x
1 Introduction	1
1.1 Related Work	1
1.2 Approach	3
2 Theoretical Foundations	5
2.1 Flow Past a Cylinder	5
2.2 Feedforward Neural Network	6
2.2.1 Activation function	8
2.2.2 Gradient Descent	8
2.2.3 Long Short Term Memory RNN - LSTM	9
3 Methodology	11
3.1 Flow Control Problem	11
3.1.1 Geometry of the Simulation	11
3.1.2 Flow Characteristics	11
3.2 Domain Discretization	13
3.3 Runtime	14
3.4 Reinforcement Learning	14
3.4.1 Environment	15
3.4.2 Agent	16
3.4.3 Adaption of Deep Reinforcement Learning Start Time Sampling Interval	18
3.4.4 Minor changes to the DRL algorithm	18
3.5 Model-based Reinforcement Learning Through Time Series Prediction	19
3.5.1 Model Training and Deployment	19
3.5.2 Initial Trajectories	19
3.5.3 Feed Forward Neural Network	19
3.5.4 Data Normalization	20
3.5.5 Data Splitting	20
3.5.6 Hyperparameter Optimization	20
3.5.7 Reduction of the Number of Pressure Sensors	21
3.5.8 Multiple Subsequent Time Steps	21
3.5.9 LSTM for Time Series Prediction	21
4 Results and Discussion	22
4.1 Generation of Initial Trajectories	22
4.2 Environment Model Training	24
4.2.1 FFNN Training	24
4.2.2 LSTM Training	33
4.2.3 Multi-step Prediction	35
4.3 Integration Into the PPO Algorithm	37
4.3.1 Model-based Sampling	37
4.3.2 Duration of Model-based Trajectory Sampling	57
5 Conclusion	58
Bibliography	xiii

List of Figures	xxii
List of Tables	xxiii
A Results Single-Step LSTM	xxiv
B Results Multi-Step LSTM	xxvi

Nomenclature

Latin Symbols

c_D	Drag coefficient
c_L	Lift coefficient
C	Cost/Loss function
d	Cylinder diameter
F_D	Drag force
F_L	Lift force
F_x	Force in x-direction
F_y	Force in y-direction
G	Return
H	Simulation height
n	Unit vector normal
N	Number of samples, Number of mesh cells, Number of label variables
p	Pressure
p^*	Dimensionless pressure
R	Reward
Re	Reynolds number, $U_\infty l/\nu$
r	Radius
S	Cylinder wall
t	Time
t^*	Dimensionless time
\mathbf{u}	Velocity vector
\mathbf{u}^*	Dimensionless velocity vector
u	Velocity in x-direction
v	Velocity in y-direction
u_∞	Free stream velocity
x, y	Cartesian Coordinates
\hat{x}, \hat{y}	Dimensionless cartesian Coordinates
x	De-normalized value
x^*	Normalized value
y	Label
y^*	Prediction

Greek Symbols

α	Parameter of the beta distribution
β	Parameter of the beta distribution

∇	Nabla operator
η	Learning rate
ν	Kinematic viscosity
π	Policy
ρ	Density
ω	Angular velocity of the cylinder

Indices

c	Coefficient
j	(L) layer neuron index
k	(L-1) layer neuron index
m	Maximal velocity at inlet, Iteration
max	Maximum
min	Minimum
p	Pressure
t	tangential,
x	y-direction
y	x-direction
∞	Free stream

Abbreviations

<i>AFC</i>	<u>A</u> ctive <u>F</u> low <u>C</u> ontrol
<i>ANN</i>	<u>A</u> rtificial <u>N</u> eural <u>N</u> etwork
<i>API</i>	<u>A</u> pplication <u>P</u> rogramming <u>I</u> nterface
<i>CFD</i>	<u>C</u> omputational <u>F</u> luid <u>D</u> ynamics
<i>CNN</i>	<u>C</u> onvolutional <u>N</u> eural <u>N</u> etwork
<i>DMD</i>	<u>D</u> ynamic <u>M</u> ode <u>D</u> ecomposition
<i>DMDc</i>	<u>D</u> ynamic <u>M</u> ode <u>D</u> ecomposition with <u>C</u> ontrol
<i>DNN</i>	<u>D</u> eep <u>N</u> eural <u>N</u> etwork
<i>DNS</i>	<u>D</u> irect <u>N</u> umerical <u>S</u> imulation
<i>DRL</i>	<u>D</u> eep <u>R</u> einforcement <u>L</u> earning
<i>FFNN</i>	<u>F</u> eed <u>F</u> orward <u>N</u> eural <u>N</u> etwork
<i>GPR</i>	<u>G</u> aussian <u>P</u> rocess <u>R</u> egression
<i>HPC</i>	<u>H</u> igh <u>P</u> erformance <u>C</u> omputing
<i>IQR</i>	<u>I</u> nter <u>Q</u> uartile <u>R</u> ange
<i>LSTM</i>	<u>L</u> ong- <u>S</u> hort- <u>T</u> erm <u>M</u> emory
<i>MAE</i>	<u>M</u> ean <u>A</u> bsolute <u>E</u> rror
<i>ML</i>	<u>M</u> achine <u>L</u> earning
<i>MLP</i>	<u>M</u> ulti <u>L</u> ayer <u>P</u> erceptron
<i>MPC</i>	<u>M</u> odel <u>P</u> redictive <u>C</u> ontrol
<i>MSE</i>	<u>M</u> ean <u>S</u> quare <u>E</u> rror
<i>NN</i>	<u>N</u> eural <u>N</u> etwork
<i>PFC</i>	<u>P</u> assive <u>F</u> low <u>C</u> ontrol
<i>PINN</i>	<u>P</u> hysics <u>I</u> nformed <u>N</u> eural <u>N</u> etwork
<i>RL</i>	<u>R</u> einforcement <u>L</u> earning
<i>PPO</i>	<u>P</u> roximal <u>P</u> olicy <u>O</u> ptimization

ReLU Rectified Linear Unit
RNN Recurrent Neural Network

1. Introduction

In 2017 aviation was responsible for 3.8% of the total EU greenhouse gas emissions [12]. Therefore aircraft manufacturers and the industry, in general, are under pressure of developing more energy-efficient ways of flying. Similar to the electrification of ground transportation, the aviation industry actively develops electric aircraft, sustainable fuels and tries to improve the efficiency of flying [12]. One way of improving the flight properties of an aircraft, e.g. reduce drag and increase lift, is to passively influence and control the flow around the aircraft by constructive measures for example vortex generators [45]. The phenomenon of passive flow control (PFC) can also be observed in nature i.e. the special structure of the skin of sharks can provide drag reduction [9]. The improvement of flight properties can also be achieved by the so-called active flow control (AFC). In AFC the flow is influenced by adding external energy to the flow by f.ex. synthetic jets [39]. Due to the complexity of finding proper control laws from sparse sensor and flow information [11], drag reduction solutions incorporating AFC have yet remained simple and do not exploit their full potential. The recent improvements in artificial intelligence (AI), especially deep reinforcement learning (DRL), and the growing availability of large computation capabilities lead to new possibilities in AFC by applying machine learning (ML) techniques to AFC. Although DRL seems to be a valid solution for overcoming the issues of AFC a major drawback remains: The flow problem is modeled using a computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulation which requires large amounts of computation power as well as long computation times. Since the DRL algorithm relies on a small, fixed amount of certain flow information and not the whole simulation, this thesis evaluates and develops approaches of supervised learning for creating a reduced environment model. This model is to be used as a surrogate for the computational costly CFD simulation environment for model-based DRL.

1.1 Related Work

It has been only a matter of time that methods of artificial intelligence, especially machine learning and deep learning (DL) found their way into the field of fluid mechanics. It has been applied to solving fluid problems and efficiently describing fluid flows by learning from given data while including and satisfying the governing partial differential equations (PDE) (e.g. Navier-Stokes equations). These so-called physics-informed neural networks (PINN) can be applied for finding data-driven solutions and the data-driven discovery of PDEs from noisy data [41]. The complexity and high dimensionality of non-linear problems in fluid mechanics make AI and DL a good match for accelerating and improving developments regarding process optimization and flow control in general [15].

Model-based DRL has as of now been often applied to comparably simple environments and games. Sun et al. [47] propose a combination of Gaussian process regression (GPR) and proximal policy optimization (PPO) applied to a pendulum environment yielding fewer environment interactions with comparable performance to normal PPO. A major disadvantage of GPR is the loss of efficiency when applied to high dimensional data due to the higher computational cost [54]. Therefore it is not really applicable to most fluid mechanical problems due to the high

dimensionality and complexity of the handled data. Furthermore, Kaiser et al. [26] developed a model-based DRL approach using video prediction with convolutional neural networks (CNN) to train a DRL agent to play Atari games.

The combination of deep reinforcement learning for AFC has been first applied by Rabault et al. [39] in 2019, where they train a DRL agent using PPO to control the unsteady wake flow in a 2D cylinder flow at a Reynolds number of $Re = 100$ using two synthetic jets on the sides. The agent varies the mass flow rate of the synthetic jets in order to control the flow resulting in a drag reduction of approximately 8%. Figure 1.1 depicts the vorticity reduction and enlargement of the low velocity region of a representative flow snapshot from [39]. Based on these findings Rabault

Figure 1.1: Comparison of the velocity field of the uncontrolled (a) and actively controlled (b) flow of a 2D cylinder flow. The mitigation in vorticity can be seen by the enlargement of the low velocity zone in the cylinder’s wake. Image source: Figure 4 from [39]

et al. [40] improved their setup by parallelizing the execution of CFD simulations and adapting the DRL algorithm to the parallelization in order to collect experiences from independent parallel simulations. This resulted in a training speed up of 20-60 times in comparison to serial training.

In [50], Tang et al. investigated the robustness of a DRL agent using the PPO algorithm for AFC at different Reynolds numbers ($Re = 100, 200, 300, 400$) using a setup with four synthetic jets. They implemented a new smoothing interpolation algorithm used to ensure continuous action sampling, in order to provide better convergence by avoiding f.ex. sudden jumps of the lift. The presented methodology provided a drag reduction from approximately 5.7% at $Re = 100$ and up to 38.7% at $Re = 400$ while having good generalization ability for flows at unseen Reynolds numbers between 60 to 400.

A different approach regarding the control action was tested by Tokarev et al. [53] at a Reynolds number of 100. They let the DRL agent control the flow through the time-dependent angular velocity resulting in oscillations around the cylinder’s axis. Applying two different reward functions provided a drag reduction of 14% and 16%, respectively, while keeping the oscillation effort and therefore the amplitude of the rotational velocity as low as 8,0% and 0,8% of the incoming flow, respectively.

Paris et al. [33] also chose to examine a 2D laminar flow around a cylinder with two synthetic jets as actuators and additionally placed pressure sensors in the wake of the cylinder to use as feedback observation. Focusing on the robustness and efficiency of the DRL algorithm, a so-called (S-PPO-CMA) algorithm was implemented, optimizing the sensor layout. This resulted in a drag reduction of 18,4% at a Reynolds number of 100. Throughout the work, it was established that the sensor layout could be reduced to a number of five sensors while keeping performance and accuracy. The proposed control strategy is also robust against Reynolds number variations in the range of 100 to 216.

A model predictive control (MPC) approach using a deep recurrent neural network (RNN) has been applied by Bieker et al. [3]. Since the high dimensionality and non-linearity of flow fields

make real-time control difficult, the RNN is used to learn dominant patterns of the flow from sensor data to feed into a model predictive control framework. Figure 1.2 illustrates the structure of the control scheme implemented in their work. The RNN has an encoder-decoder architecture for multi-step prediction. The framework has been evaluated using different CFD simulation setups as well as Reynolds numbers, e.g. the 2D flow past a cylinder similar to this thesis. The control is applied by rotating the cylinder and the relevant control parameters are the drag and lift forces acting on the cylinder, respectively. The developed MPC approach using a deep RNN

Figure 1.2: Structure of the MPC control scheme by Bieker et al. [3]; Image source: Figure 1 from [3]

as a surrogate model for the environment yielded good results regarding accuracy between the predicted and real drag and lift values. The approach reduces computational complexity and dependence on the flow field’s scale like time step and grid size [3]

The two most recent approaches on AFC through DRL are by Ghraieb et al. [16] and Qin et al. [38] published throughout 2021. Ghraieb et al. implemented a single-step PPO algorithm that does not rely on the state of the system, therefore being only applicable in open-loop control problems. The method is first applied to two test cases (NACA 0012 airfoil, two side-by-side circular cylinders in laminar regimes) in order to reach a certain level of robustness and accuracy before being applied to more complex cases. After that, it is applied to two setups of a circular and a square cylinder having each a smaller control cylinder at $Re = 22000$ and a triangular arrangement of three cylinders, the so-called fluid pinball. Applied to the rectangular cylinder case a drag reduction of up to 30% could be reached. By rotating the front cylinder and counter-rotating cylinders in the wake a drag reduction of up to 60% could be reached for the triangular arrangement.

Qin et al. [38] use a kind of model-based approach for AFC with DRL by including pressure sensor information from the wake of the 2D cylinder flow case using an algorithm called dynamic mode decomposition with control (DMDC) which was introduced by Proctor et al. [37]. It is based on the regular dynamic mode decomposition (DMD) by Schmid [44] which is a data-driven approach for equation-free complex dynamics modeling. DMD tries to find the best-fit linear operator A for the equation $x_{k+1} \approx Ax_k$. x_{t+1} is the state at time step $t + 1$ and x is the state at time step t . DMDC extends this concept by taking into account a control input u_t through the relation $x_{t+1} \approx Ax_t + Bu_t$ [37]. Qin et al. also examine a 2D laminar flow past a cylinder simulation with two synthetic jets. The presented method uses information extracted from the wake of the cylinder through DMDC in order to calculate the reward leveraging the advantage to integrate a control input and flow field information.

1.2 Approach

This thesis is based on the work of Darshan Thummar [8] and Fabian Gabriel [14] therefore the simulation environment and large parts of the PPO algorithm will be adopted.

In order to create a reduced-order model a set of initial trajectories has to be created by conducting an initial training of the current DRL agent using the regular CFD environment. As a first step, a feed-forward neural network will be implemented in order to regressively predict the pressure values for all 400 sensors as well as drag and lift coefficients for each next time step of a few random trajectory from all 400 pressure sensor values and the taken action by the DRL in the initial trajectories. As a next step, the same model is used for autoregressive prediction and the results are compared. In order to keep the temporal evolution and behavior of the pressure distribution along the cylinder's surface and of the drag and lift coefficients, multiple subsequent time steps are going to be integrated into the model's input feature vector. Since the amount of data that is included in a single state (400 pressure sensors and the action) is high and gets higher for multiple subsequent time steps, a reduction of the feature space is going to be investigated. In order to investigate another approach for time series forecasting, two different RNN long-short-term-memory (LSTM) architectures (single-step and multi-step) are tested for their applicability on the test case. The next step is to train the policy and value networks of the DRL agent using only the learned reduced-order model which is then compared to the simulation environment.

2. Theoretical Foundations

The following chapter introduces elementary theories and fundamental concepts.

2.1 Flow Past a Cylinder

The simple problem of a 2D flow past a cylinder and its wide application among literature makes it a good test and benchmark case for active flow control [3, 16, 33, 38, 39, 40, 43, 50, 53]. The flow field for this test case can be characterized by the Reynolds number, which is the dimensionless form of the velocity:

$$Re = \frac{u_\infty d}{\nu}, \quad (2.1)$$

where u_∞ denotes the average flow velocity at the inlet, d denotes the characteristic length, here the cylinder's diameter and ν denotes the kinematic viscosity. Figure 2.1 depicts the simulated flow past a cylinder at low Re ($Re = 50$), where the formation of a symmetric flow field can be observed. The flow originates at the inlet on the left and moves from there until the outlet on the right. In the adjacent wake behind the cylinder, a region with low flow velocities can be observed originating from the obstacle in the flow.

Figure 2.1: Velocity magnitude of a simulated 2D flow past a cylinder in a channel at $Re = 50$. High flow velocities are depicted in red and low velocities in blue. Image source: Fig. 2.1 from [14]

Vortex Shedding

For larger Reynolds numbers a phenomenon called vortex shedding can be observed. It describes the formation of an oscillating flow in the wake leading to alternating counter-rotating vortices propagating downstream in the cylinder's wake, also known as a von Kármán vortex street. As the Reynolds numbers rise the frequency of vortex shedding and the size of the vortices increases also. Photographs visualizing vortex streets with increasing Re can be seen in Figure 2.2. Before the vortex shedding begins the adjacent flow region behind the cylinder contains two symmetric counter-circulating recirculation bubbles. At increasing Re the length of the cavity increases until the boundary layer on the cylinder's walls becomes unsteady and starts to detach itself from the wall inducing vortex shedding [57] (see Figure 2.3a). As the vortex shedding develops a growing vortex on the one side opens the cavity making way for the opposite vortex to push fluid into the cavity which then fuels the previous vortex' development. A depiction of the

Figure 2.2: Photographs of vortex street visualization: (a) Aluminum flake visualization of a vortex street at $Re = 150$, (b) at $Re = 300$, (c) at $Re = 4000$, (d) Schlieren photograph of a vortex street at $Re = 270000$. Image source: Fig. 1 from [57]

process, showing the interpretation of the phenomenon as instantaneous streamlines, can be seen in Figure 2.3b. At some point the vortex grows large enough and cuts of the fluid supply into the cavity, cutting the vortex off of the cavity and moving downstream. This oscillating process then repeats for each side of the cylinder.

(a) Flow regions around the cylinder with steady and unsteady wake. Image source: Part of Fig. 4 from [57]

(b) Vortex shedding interpreted as a process of instantaneous streamlines. Image source: Fig. 2 from [57]

Figure 2.3

2.2 Feedforward Neural Network

Feedforward neural networks (FFNN) or Deep (artificial) neural networks (DNN) are computation structures for approximating a function $f(\cdot)$ in the way that it maps some input x to an output y so that $y = f^*(x, \theta)$ applies with f^* being the approximation function for f and θ are the parameters to be learned by the FFNN [17]. This input to output mapping is achieved by cascadingly applying several small functions onto the input through $y = f_1(f_2(f_3(x)))$. These cascading functions are implemented in a network that is structured into one to several lay-

ers and one to several neurons and a bias unit per layer that are connected like a graph with weighted neuron-neuron connections by the weights w_{jk} . Each neuron is affected by a bias unit which describes how easy it is to trigger the neuron's activation [30]. An example neural network consisting of six input features, two hidden layers, and five outputs is depicted in Figure 2.4. In order to train a DNN with supervised learning, the training data must consist of the input

Figure 2.4: Example of a fully connected deep feedforward neural network with 2 hidden layers. The input dimension is six, the hidden layer dimensions are equally ten and the output dimension is five. The bias is depicted as the top neuron of each layer except for the last, since they are not connected to the previous layers. Image created using [28].

feature vector \mathbf{x} of which each is accompanied by a label stored in the corresponding label vector \mathbf{y} . During training the neural network takes the input feature vector \mathbf{x} and tries to find a good approximation $\mathbf{y} \approx f^*(\mathbf{x})$. The network, therefore, has a reference for the outcome and adapts the parameters of the network accordingly. The goal is to minimize the prediction error, called loss or cost, in reference to the corresponding label. The loss is calculated using different loss functions for example the mean square error (MSE), which penalizes big errors more or the mean absolute error (MAE), which reduces the dominance of larger errors [10]. The MSE can be calculated by

$$MSE = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N (y^* - y)^2, \quad (2.2)$$

where N is the number of samples, y^* is the prediction and y is the target label and the MAE by

$$MAE = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N |(y^* - y)|. \quad (2.3)$$

In a regression task, an FFNN applying these loss functions, therefore, tries to minimize the L_2 (euclidean) or L_1 distance between prediction and target. The loss or cost function is of now denoted as C . There are many more ways to determine and evaluate the prediction error for which some are more suitable for classification tasks (e.g. minimum cross-entropy) which are not considered in this project, wherefore I here refer to [24]. The loss function for DRL follows a different scheme and it is going to be introduced later on in Subsection 3.4.1 therefore it is not described here.

A neural network has several parameters that affect learning in different ways. From these, some are adapted during training, the weights, and some are adapted before training, called hyperparameters. The weights are the parameters that are actually learned and adapted while

the network is training. The hyperparameters affect how the network is structured and how the network conducts the learning. Some examples for hyperparameters are the learning rate, batch size, number of neurons, number of hidden layers, the optimizer, or the activation function.

2.2.1 Activation function

The aforementioned activation function defines the output of a neuron by applying a transformation function $f(\cdot)$ onto the summed input of the neuron. Non-linear transformations are applied for being able to model complex non-linear behaviors [30, 17]. Examples are the sigmoid function, which scales the input to the range between $[0, 1]$, tangens hyperbolicus (\tanh), scaling to $[-1, 1]$ or the rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) function which just returns the positive part of the argument it receives [18]:

$$g(z) = \max(0, z). \quad (2.4)$$

The ReLU function can be seen in Figure 2.5. ReLU activation functions have the advantage

Figure 2.5: Rectified linear unit activation function; Image source: [17]

that they avoid the problem of vanishing gradients since they do not scale the input to a range between $[0, 1]$ or $[-1, 1]$ but just return the input if its greater > 0 . Gradient vanishing describes the phenomenon for larger networks of a decreasing sensitivity of the weights with respect to the loss, which becomes more severe as the number of hidden layers increases. This leads to decreasing weight updates until no learning can be conducted. The gradient for sigmoid and \tanh may saturate for very large and very small inputs [18] leading to vanishing gradients in backpropagation.

2.2.2 Gradient Descent

Neural networks learn through gradient descent optimization using error backpropagation [10]. The neural network computes the gradient of a loss or cost function - these terms are used equivalently - with respect to the weights in order to find a good minimum of the loss function. The cost function here is not convex in contrast to linear methods (e.g. support vector machines) [10, 7], meaning that a neural network only finds local minima of the cost function but according to [7] local minima are often of equal quality.

Therefore gradient descent tries to minimize the cost function by adapting the weights in small steps towards the minimum through

$$\Delta \mathbf{w} = -\eta \frac{\partial C}{\partial \mathbf{w}} \quad (2.5)$$

where η is the learning rate defining the step size, which needs to be small enough to not overshoot the minimum but also large enough to not slow down the processing too much. C is the cost function and \mathbf{w} are the weights. The weights for each layer for each iteration m are then updated by the following rule:

$$\mathbf{w}_{m+1} = \mathbf{w}_m + \Delta \mathbf{w}_m = \mathbf{w}_m - \eta \frac{\partial C}{\partial \mathbf{w}_m} \quad (2.6)$$

In order to reduce vanishing gradients, improve performance for non-stationary learning objectives, and speed-up training, the gradient descent method can be enhanced by applying the Adam optimizer by [27]. Adam stands for adaptive moment estimation and it applies varying learning rates throughout training by estimating exponentially moving first-order momentum (mean) and second-order raw momentum (uncentered variance) of the gradient. The decay rates of these moving averages are controlled by the parameters β_1 and β_2 [27, 5]. Adam proves to be highly effective yielding better performance and faster convergence compared to other stochastic optimization methods, which can be seen in Figure 2.6.

Figure 2.6: Performance of the Adam optimizer in comparison to other methods. Image source: Figure 2(a) from [27]

Backpropagation

Backpropagation is a special form of automatic differentiation where the chain rule is used to calculate the derivatives analytically layer by layer [30, 17]. For backpropagation the neural network needs to calculate the gradient of the cost function with respect to all weights of the neural network where each entry of the gradient is called sensitivity of the cost function with respect to a certain weight [17, 30, 1]. The gradient of C is

$$\nabla C = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial C}{\partial w_{jk}^{(1)}} \\ \vdots \\ \frac{\partial C}{\partial w_{jk}^{(L)}} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.7)$$

where C is the cost or loss, $w_{jk}^{(L)}$ are all weights for each neuron for each layer. The upper indices in round parentheses (L) correspond to the layers of the neural network, the subscript index j corresponds to the neurons of the (L) layer and the subscript index k to the neurons of the ($L - 1$) layer. Therefore $w_{jk}^{(L)}$ is the weight of the connection between neuron k of layer ($L - 1$) and neuron j of layer (L) and so on. The backpropagation algorithm only refers to the process of computing the derivatives, in this case, of the cost function [17]. For further information on the backpropagation algorithm I hereby refer to chapter 6.5 from [17].

2.2.3 Long Short Term Memory RNN - LSTM

An LSTM is a special kind of a Recurrent Neural Network (RNN). In contrast to an FFNN, it has internal recurrent structures providing short-term memory capabilities in order to capture the temporal information between subsequent features. The basic structure of an RNN can be observed in Figure 2.7

Figure 2.7: Example of the structure of a recurrent neural network. The unfolded network is depicted on the right side. Image source: [56]

The layered structure of an RNN can be misleading since the unfolding is an unfolding in time meaning that the layers are not real layers but instances of the same RNN in time. RNNs suffer from the problem of vanishing and exploding gradients that is if the gradients for backpropagation are arbitrarily small the weights will no longer be updated. If the gradients are arbitrarily large the weight updates can get therefore arbitrarily large leading to exploding gradients [17, 34].

LSTMs are an extension of regular RNNs developed by Hochreiter & Schmidhuber in 1997 [19]. The term LSTM stands for long-short-term memory. LSTMs implement the two types of memory by using three different gates (an input gate, forget gate, an output gate) and an inner cell. The cell can store long-term information and the three gates control the information flow in and out of the cell. A big advantage of LSTMs over regular RNNs is that they mitigate the problem of vanishing and exploding gradients by providing a constant error flow [19]. The general structure of an LSTM cell is depicted in Figure 2.8. The gates are implemented using sigmoid and tanh functions, being single neural network layers, for deciding which input to keep and forget at which magnitude. The forget gate regulates which information of the cell state to forget and which not

Figure 2.8: Example of the structure of an LSTM recurrent neural network. Image source: [56]

to forget by using the sigmoid activation function which normalizes the input it gets to a range between $[0, 1]$, on the input and the previous hidden state. In the next step, a sigmoid input layer combined with a tanh layer is deciding which new information to let into the cell state. The last step is the output of the cell state that is filtered by a tanh and sigmoid function, to decide which information to let out [31]. For further information on LSTMs and their implementations I here refer to [31, 19] and chapter 10.10 of [17].

3. Methodology

The following chapter describes the methodology of the CFD simulation, the DRL algorithm, which is based on the works of [8] and [14], as well as the development of the neural networks for temporal modeling of the environment.

3.1 Flow Control Problem

The examined flow control problem is a two-dimensional, incompressible flow past a circular cylinder in a rectangular channel with one inlet on the left and one outlet on the right. It has been chosen due to its simplicity, therefore, keeping computational expenses at a low level. In order to provide comparability with other works (e.g. [39, 50]), the environment is identical to the two-dimensional setup from “Benchmark Computations of Laminar Flow Around a Cylinder” by [43].

3.1.1 Geometry of the Simulation

The cylinder has a diameter of $d = 0.1$ m which is used as a reference length to make all distances dimensionless by

$$\tilde{x} = \frac{x}{d}. \quad (3.1)$$

The setup is illustrated in Figure 3.1. The simulation environment has a length of 22 and a height of 4.1. The cylinder is not completely centered in the y direction yielding a wall distance of 1.6 to the top and 1.5 to the bottom, respectively. The distance to the inlet on the left is 1.5.

Figure 3.1: Geometry of the simulation environment. All dimensions are given relative to the cylinder’s diameter. Image is based on Figure 3.1 from [14]

3.1.2 Flow Characteristics

The examined simulated fluid flow is assumed to be an incompressible, newtonic fluid with a density of $\rho = 1.0 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}^3}$ and a kinematic viscosity of $\nu = 10^{-2} \frac{\text{m}^2}{\text{s}}$. The free stream velocity is denoted by u_∞ and the time t is made dimensionless by

$$t^* = \frac{t}{d} \cdot u_\infty. \quad (3.2)$$

The dimensionless conservation of mass and moment equations are obtained by substituting

$$\mathbf{u}^* = \frac{\mathbf{u}}{u_\infty}, \quad (3.3)$$

$$\nabla^* = d\nabla, \quad (3.4)$$

where d denotes the diameter, and

$$p^* = \frac{p \cdot d}{\nu \cdot \rho \cdot u_\infty}. \quad (3.5)$$

The variable \mathbf{u}^* describes the dimensionless form of the velocity, described by $\mathbf{u} = (u, v)^T$ where u and v describe the velocity in x-direction and y-direction, respectively (see Figure 3.1). p^* and ∇^* denote the dimensionless representations of the pressure p and the gradient ∇ . Applying the aforementioned transformations, the dimensionless continuity equation and conservation of momentum equation become

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}^* = 0 \quad (3.6)$$

and

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{u}^*}{\partial t} + (\mathbf{u}^* \cdot \nabla^*) \mathbf{u}^* = -\nabla^* p^* + \frac{1}{Re} \nabla^{*2} \mathbf{u}^*. \quad (3.7)$$

In order to calculate the drag and lift coefficients, the drag force F_D and lift force F_L have to be calculated first. Similar to [43], the drag force acting in x-direction on the cylinder can be calculated as the integral over the cylinder's wall by

$$F_D = F_x = \int_S (\rho \nu \frac{\partial v_t}{\partial n} n_y - p n_x) dS \quad (3.8)$$

where n denotes the unit vector normal of the outer surface of the cylinder, which can be decomposed into its x- and y-components n_x and n_y , and v_t denotes the velocity tangential to the cylinder's surface. The lift force acting in y-direction is calculated in a similar fashion:

$$F_L = F_y = - \int_S (\rho \nu \frac{\partial v_t}{\partial n} n_x + p n_y) dS. \quad (3.9)$$

Eventually the drag and lift forces are normalized to the drag and lift coefficients through

$$c_D = \frac{2F_D}{\rho u_\infty^2 d} \quad (3.10)$$

and

$$c_L = \frac{2F_L}{\rho u_\infty^2 d}. \quad (3.11)$$

Boundary Conditions

A no-slip boundary condition has been applied to the top and bottom wall of the channel as well as on the cylinder's surface. This means that the velocity in x- and y-direction are equal to zero at these positions:

$$\mathbf{u}^* = (0, 0)^T \quad (3.12)$$

and

$$\frac{dp^*}{dn} = (0, 0)^T \quad (3.13)$$

applies. The vector $\tilde{\mathbf{x}} = (\tilde{x}, \tilde{y})^T$ denotes a position. The inlet velocity distribution, similar to [43], is parabolic and being defined as:

$$\mathbf{u}^*(0, \tilde{y}) = \begin{pmatrix} 4U_m y(H - y) \cdot \frac{1}{H^2} \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \cdot \frac{1}{u_\infty} \quad (3.14)$$

U_m denotes the maximal velocity determined by $U_m = 1.5 \cdot u_\infty$ and H denotes the height of the simulation environment. Furthermore the pressure does not change over the inlet yielding:

$$\frac{dp^*}{dx} = 0. \quad (3.15)$$

At last the boundary condition at the outlet is defined so that the gradient of the dimensionless velocity and the pressure equal zero:

$$\frac{d\mathbf{u}^*}{dx} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (3.16)$$

$$p^* = 0 \quad (3.17)$$

3.2 Domain Discretization

The discretization of the simulation environment is conducted using the CFD library OpenFOAM and it is identical to the outcome of the mesh dependency study by [14]. For the spatial discretization, the whole flow domain is split into two subdomains: One quadratic domain around the cylinder and another rectangular domain reaching to the outlet. Figure 3.2 shows an example discretization with $N_x = 275$ and $N_y = 50$ which illustrates the structure. N_x and N_y denote the number of cells in x- and y-direction, respectively. It is discretized using a structured mesh of rectangles where the average velocity and pressure of the cell are assumed to apply constantly over the whole cell. The mesh is further refined around the cylinder in direction of the cylinder's surface yielding half the thickness of the cells located on the left, top, and bottom walls. The thickness of the cells in the cylinder's trail is further increased until reaching eight times the thickness of the cells at the cylinder's surface at the outlet. The number of cells in x-direction

Figure 3.2: Example mesh with $N_x = 275$ and $N_y = 50$. Image source: Figure 3.2 from [14]

depends on the number of cells in y-direction by

$$N_x = N_y + \frac{2.2 - 0.4}{0.4} \cdot N_y \quad (3.18)$$

The mesh dependency study of [14] showed that a discretization with $N_y = 100$ and therefore $N_x = 550$ yields a good balance between computation time and accuracy therefore being also selected for this work. If the CFL condition is not satisfied the numerical method is not stable therefore the time step has been chosen to be $\Delta t = 2.5 \cdot 10^{-4} s$ yielding a maximal CFL number of approximately $CFL \approx 0.6$.

3.3 Runtime

Most relevant simulations and calculations are conducted using the high-performance computing (HPC) cluster of the TU Braunschweig yielding 244.5 TFLOPS or on a personal computer with an Intel[®] Core[™]i7-8565U CPU with 1.80GHz x 8 and 8 GB RAM. Further information on the HPC cluster can be found at [51]. Furthermore, several libraries and tools are used in this work which are not explained in depth but should be mentioned for the sake of reproducibility and documentation.

Singularity

The repository storing the runtime environment is deployed using the container platform Singularity. Singularity is an open-source platform initially developed at the Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory in Berkely, California, USA [49]. The tool provides containering capabilities, especially for the use on HPC clusters. In contrast to the widely used container platform docker, Singularity just provides the users with user access rights and does not require to elevate users to higher levels of accessibility [49, 55]. Since HPC clusters are usually used by multiple users with processing capacity scheduling, Singularity provides a higher level of security on HPC clusters. The singularity version 3.6.0rc2 has been used throughout this thesis.

Open MPI

In order to provide fast computation through parallelization of the execution of the DRL algorithm, the setup uses the open-source library Open MPI. Open MPI implements a high-quality message passing interface framework for parallel computing handling process control, resource management, failure management, etc. [52, 13]. The calculations for this thesis have been conducted using OpenMPI version 4.0.1.

OpenFOAM

The numerical calculations for the flow control problem are conducted using the open-source continuous continuum mechanics and CFD library OpenFOAM developed by the OpenCFD Ltd. OpenFOAM provides a variety of software tools developed in C++ to handle complex fluid flows including turbulence transfer, chemical reactions, acoustics and more [32, 25]. The results in this thesis have been produced using OpenFOAM version *v1912*.

PyTorch

The DRL algorithm and the FFNN model for the model-based DRL algorithm are implemented using PyTorch. It is an open-source machine learning framework developed in python and C++ by Facebook's AI research team based on the ML library torch implemented in the programming language Lua [21]. PyTorch combines straightforward usability and speed through a pythonic API and an efficient C++ core [35]. As a result, PyTorch is nowadays a flexible and widely used ML library [46]. Throughout this thesis PyTorch version 1.6.0 has been used.

3.4 Reinforcement Learning

The control law for actively controlling the flow past the cylinder is learned by means of DRL. Reinforcement learning (RL), besides supervised and unsupervised learning, is one of the three main paradigms in which machine learning can currently be divided into [48]. Supervised and unsupervised learning basically try to find or reproduce certain patterns by processing labeled or unlabeled data, respectively. In RL the core components are the acting agent and the environment which is influenced by the agent's action. An agent, which basically is some kind of

program being able to carry out certain actions, has the goal to learn a task by acting in order to maximize a certain reward signal [29]. The chosen action is penalized using the defined reward signal. For example, an action that is denoted as “good” generates a high reward signal and an action that is denoted as “bad” a low reward signal. Deep reinforcement learning (DRL) is the extension of RL using deep neural networks in order to learn a task. After the agent acted on the environment, it transitions into a new state and returns a reward. The agent receives an observation of the environment, being a partially observed state, and the reward. The observation and the reward are then used to improve the agent’s control strategy. An illustration of this process can be seen in Figure 3.3. In RL the agent constantly tries to balance the trade-off between

Figure 3.3: Agent-environment interaction.

exploration and exploitation. It means that the agent can exploit its knowledge by choosing an action yielding a high reward, although another action, that it has not already explored may yield an even higher reward. Only exploring might result in very high rewards in some cases but in others, it might also result in very low rewards. On the contrary, only exploiting the action yielding the highest reward that the agent knows of will most certainly not result in the best possible reward overall.

3.4.1 Environment

The environment is represented by the flow simulation. The agent is able to interact with the environment by changing the rotational velocity ω of the cylinder and therefore changing the no-slip boundary condition on the cylinder’s wall through:

$$u^* = \omega r \quad (3.19)$$

where u^* denotes the surface velocity and r the cylinder’s radius. Positive rotational velocities lead to a clockwise rotation and vice versa. The state of the complete simulation environment is not available to the agent, it is only able to access the information of the surface pressure of the cylinder. These are quantified by the pressure in the grid cells on the cylinder’s surface, which are also referred to as pressure sensors. For the chosen grid size of $N_y = 100$ the state is quantified by the pressure values of 400 pressure sensors. The pressure sensors do not change their position if the agent manipulates the rotational velocity of the cylinder which leads to an easier approximation of the dependency between the state and the action by the agent.

Horizon

The horizon of the agent describes the number of time steps the agent is able to plan for. It can either be finite or infinite depending on the termination condition of the agent. In this case, one whole simulation run, which is denoted as a *trajectory*, corresponds to the planning horizon of the agent. The horizon has been chosen to be finite since the overall goal of the agent is to reduce the drag and the oscillatory behavior of the coefficients in general and not by a certain amount.

Reward and Return Function

In order to penalize or reward the actions of the agent the following reward function is used:

$$R_t = 3 - (c_D + 0.1|c_L|) \quad (3.20)$$

The agent’s task is to reduce the drag and oscillations in the coefficients, therefore the drag c_D and lift c_L coefficients are included in the reward function. The drag is weighted higher than the lift as can be seen in Equation 3.20. The reward function is returned by the environment.

In order to take the influence of future actions into consideration not only the reward but the cumulative reward, or return, is also returned by the environment. It is calculated by summing over all weighted rewards:

$$G_\tau = \sum_{t=0}^T \gamma^t R_t \quad (3.21)$$

The discount factor γ weights the rewards of future actions through the exponent T which is continually decreased meaning that rewards in the near future are more important than actions in the distant future [29]. The discount factor for training the DRL agent has been set to $\gamma = 0.99$

3.4.2 Agent

The agent is the program that learns to control the flow around the cylinder through deep reinforcement learning. In this case, the learning algorithm *Proximal Policy Optimization* (PPO) is used to train the agent.

Learning through PPO

PPO is a so-called actor-critic algorithm consisting of two neural networks: A policy network, the actor, and a value network, which is the critic. On the one hand, actor-critic algorithms try to model the dependency between the state and the return, through the value network, and on the other hand between the action and the return through the policy network. PPO is a policy gradient optimization method with clipped gradient updates, meaning that policy updates cannot diverge too large from the current policy in order to keep the training stable and learn more gradually. In order for the agent to learn it needs to gather experiences by applying the current policy π_k to the environment. This is conducted ten times in parallel, meaning in ten separate environments, to exploit the parallelization advantage of experience gathering of PPO. During a simulation run the state, action, and reward are computed and saved after each RL time step. After one trajectory has been completed all rewards and returns of the taken actions are computed and saved. The actions are sampled from a beta distribution over the normalized interval $[0, 1]$, from which they are transformed back to the original range between $\omega = [-10, 10]$. During training the action is sampled randomly from the beta distribution, which is parameterized by α and β . At deployment, the mean of the beta distribution is the action. A depiction of the algorithm can be seen in Figure 3.4. Further information on the application of the beta distribution to this case can be gathered in the previous work of Fabian Gabriel [14]. After all parallel trajectories are completed the so-called replay buffer is filled with the experiences from the trajectories containing the states, taken actions, rewards, returns and, log probabilities of the actions that were generated with the current control policy. The current policy is updated using the information from the replay buffer and eventually, the next episode begins. The application of the PPO algorithm is further described in the work of Darshan Thummar [8], on which this thesis is based on.

Figure 3.4: Flowchart of the PPO algorithm. Based on figure 3.4 on page 20 from [14]

Policy Network

As mentioned before the policy network functions as the actor. It consists of an input layer of 400 neurons, taking in the 400 pressure values along the cylinder’s surface, two hidden layers with each 64 neurons, and an output layer with two neurons which are the α and β parameters of the beta distribution.

Value Network

The value network, in contrast to the policy network, has an input layer of one neuron which corresponds to the calculated return after one trajectory, two hidden layers with each 64 neurons, and an output layer of two neurons. The value network approximates the state-value function for the given policy, therefore being a mapping between the state, consisting of the pressure values, and the value, which is the expected return, therefore a scalar value. Policy and value network are trained separately which can also be observed in Figure 3.4

Time step

To stabilize and improve training, the agent does not control the flow at every numerical time step but only every 20th time step by:

$$\Delta t_{\text{Agent}} = 20 \cdot \Delta t_{CFD} = 20 \cdot 2.5 \cdot 10^{-4} s \cdot \frac{u_{\infty}}{d} = 5 * 10^{-2} \quad (3.22)$$

This trick is used to reduce the amount of data produced, to apply a realistic behavior of the actuation since the actuation frequency would physically be restricted, and since the physical properties and changes of the flow should be relevant for the agent to learn and not the numerical properties of the simulation. Therefore, the control time step is set to a smaller value than the characteristic frequency of vortex shedding, similar to [53]. The angular velocity is changed continuously between two actions in order to keep the simulation scenario more realistic and avoid sudden jumps of the pressure, drag, and lift coefficients.

3.4.3 Adaption of Deep Reinforcement Learning Start Time Sampling Interval

After an evaluation of the results of a previous thesis on the topic by [14] and [55] it has been decided to improve the DRL algorithm by randomly sampling the training start times and expanding the start time interval for the training of the DRL agent from [4.5, 4.9] to [2.5, 4.9]. This leads to better generalization capabilities of the agent by reducing dependencies on the training start time and by including early information on the formation of the von Kármán vortex street into the learning procedure of the agent. Furthermore, the seed for PyTorch’s internal pseudo-random number generator for the random sampling has been set to a value of zero at the beginning of the training in order to ensure reproducibility.

3.4.4 Minor changes to the DRL algorithm

In order to increase the stability of the training of the DRL agent a softplus activation function ($\log(1 + \exp(x))$) is applied and the value 1 is added to the output of the policy network. This change results in the policy model directly predicting the values of the parameters α and β of the beta distribution and making sure their values are always > 1 . This improvement leads to a beta distribution that is unimodal and concave [36]. Therefore the action sampling process of the DRL agent is ensured to be more continuous by avoiding sampling of sudden extreme values for the action. The aforementioned changes have been applied after the initial trajectories had been created due to too high rewards during DRL training with the environment model which is described in more detail in Subsection 3.5.1. Therefore the initial trajectories do not include these stabilization measures.

3.5 Model-based Reinforcement Learning Through Time Series Prediction

The goal is to use a neural network to predict the future states of the pressure along the cylinder’s surface as well as the drag and lift coefficients from the previous temporal states. In order to conduct this time series prediction at first, a feed-forward neural network (FFNN) is used. The FFNN functions as a surrogate environment model, sometimes also called control model. In order to test another approach two LSTM architectures (single- and multi-step) are evaluated as well.

3.5.1 Model Training and Deployment

All different NN architectures (FFNN, single-step and multi-step LSTM) are trained using supervised learning by predicting the next state from the previous states. The train data, therefore, consists of pairs of features and labels, where the feature is the sequence of subsequent states plus the chosen action by the DRL agent and the label contains the correct values for the next state, containing the pressure values and c_D and c_L . Only the labels for the multi-step LSTM contain more than one state since the multi-step prediction is tested against a sequence of subsequent states. In contrast to the training procedure, at deployment, the environment model shall predict sequences of subsequent time steps step-by-step from its prediction autoregressively. Therefore the model is tested and used by giving it a single start sequence of states and predicting future values step-by-step in order to predict whole trajectories of defined length. This procedure is necessary since the prediction during training and feeding it back into the network has been too computationally expensive with the current setup. Furthermore, batch training would not be feasible since the features would be generated at training time.

3.5.2 Initial Trajectories

In order to train the FFNN for time-series prediction and to use it as an environment model for the DRL agent, an initial set of trajectories, where the agent has controlled the flow past the cylinder, is created. The set of trajectories consists of ≈ 1000 trajectories since the setup is controlled by the DRL algorithm for 100 episodes with ten agents working in parallel.

3.5.3 Feed Forward Neural Network

As a start, an FFNN with an input dimension of 401, holding all pressure values $p_1 - p_{400}$ available for a state and the corresponding action, the angular velocity of the cylinder ω , is used. The output dimension is 402, consisting of the 400 pressure values and the drag coefficient c_D and lift coefficient c_L . Furthermore, the initial model consists of five hidden layers each having 50 neurons. All layers are fully connected. A depiction of the structure of the initial model can be seen in Figure 3.5.

A learning rate of $\eta = 0.0001$ is applied and the model is trained for 10000 epochs. The model is optimized using the adaptive momentum or *Adam* optimizer and the loss is calculated using MSE. The batch size is initially set to 32 and the ReLu activation function is applied on each layer. The combined input for the environment model is called the feature vector, tensor, or just feature. The model, therefore, applies a mapping from the feature to approximate the true value, called the label. At first, the state of only one time step is included in the input feature vector to prove the feasibility of a neural network predicting the next temporal state from the previous one. To improve prediction accuracy, sequences of subsequent states are included in the feature vector by stacking subsequent states, including the taken action, on top of each other.

Furthermore, the number of input pressure values is going to be investigated and adjusted with respect to memory consumption. The number of neurons used per hidden layer and the loss

Figure 3.5: Reduced depiction of initial feedforward neural network structure. The input layer on the left has the dimension 401 and the output dimension on the right is 402. The hidden layer size is 50 for each hidden layer. Image created using [28].

function is later also going to be adjusted to examine their impact on the model prediction accuracy.

3.5.4 Data Normalization

Before the FFNN can be trained the training data has to be normalized in order to improve prediction accuracy by equalizing feature weighting, since the action ω , the pressure values p_i , drag coefficient c_D and lift coefficient c_L yield different scales. Otherwise, the backpropagation would emphasize larger features more than smaller ones [6, 4]. In this case a min-max-normalization to the range $[-1, 1]$ has been applied to all features, predictions and labels using

$$x^* = 2 \cdot \left(\frac{x - x_{min}}{x_{max} - x_{min}} \right) - 1. \quad (3.23)$$

Each physical quantity (p, ω, c_D, c_L) is scaled to their min-max range using all available values corresponding to the quantity from all used initial trajectories in a training run. The denormalization is conducted vice versa

$$x = \frac{(x^* + 1)(x_{max} - x_{min})}{2} + x_{min}. \quad (3.24)$$

3.5.5 Data Splitting

In order to train and evaluate the network performance, the data has to be split into three different data sets: A training set, validation set, and test set. The training set is used for model training in order to learn the approximation function. The validation set is used to get an unbiased evaluation of the model's performance during training. This set can be for example used to tackle overfitting. The test set is used to finally evaluate the model's performance on unseen data [22].

For training the FFNN the data has been split into portions of 80% for the training set, yielding data from 794 trajectories and 20% for the test set, yielding data from 198 trajectories. For validation during training, 10% of the data dedicated for training is put aside and tested against.

3.5.6 Hyperparameter Optimization

Finding a set of hyperparameters for a neural network can be a challenging task and requires a certain level of experience but there are different systematic approaches to find good combinations of hyperparameters. Example methods for conducting hyperparameter optimization are

manual search, grid search, or random search. Manual search is a trial-and-error search by hand. Grid search basically searches a grid of hyperparameters trying every possible combination of hyperparameters which gets less feasible for larger parameter spaces [23]. In contrast, random search examines the hyperparameter space randomly, being also able to handle larger parameter spaces. There are also more sophisticated methods (e.g. latin hypercube sampling, bayesian optimization, evolutionary optimization) which are not described in detail here but can be looked up here [20, 2]. The hyperparameters for this project have been mostly tuned by hand, varying their values in narrow intervals, due to the high dimensionality of the data which would have required a serious amount of computation time when testing out a large hyperparameter space.

3.5.7 Reduction of the Number of Pressure Sensors

In order to reduce computational complexity and memory consumption the reduction of the number of pressure sensors of a single state used for prediction has been investigated. Therefore the network maps from lower dimensional state information (e.g 16 pressure sensors and action ω) to the full state with 400 pressure sensors and the drag and lift coefficients. The chosen pressure sensors have been chosen uniformly along the cylinder's surface.

3.5.8 Multiple Subsequent Time Steps

It is assumed that the prediction accuracy in general increases with an increasing number of time steps included in the model input. In order to improve prediction accuracy the feature vector has therefore been extended in order to hold the state information of subsequent time steps. This will include the temporal dependencies between subsequent states, therefore the environment model has access to more previous information to predict from.

3.5.9 LSTM for Time Series Prediction

To test another approach for time-series prediction and autoregression an RNN architecture has been tested. As already mentioned in Subsection 2.2.3 RNNs and especially LSTMs have internal recurrences to include temporal or series information of subsequent states in their architecture. Instead of a classical RNN an LSTM has been tested for time series prediction. Two architectural approaches for LSTMs, single and multi-step prediction, have been briefly tested. The difference between the two approaches, in general, is that single-step approaches try to predict only one time step ahead from a sequence of previous time steps. The Multi-step approach tries to predict not only the state of the next time step but also two, three, four, twenty, etc. time steps ahead. The NN architecture differs in the fact that the single-step architecture yields a single or several stacked LSTM cells with a single state output. The multi-step architecture is implemented by an encoder-decoder structure as in [42]. The encoder gets the state as input and outputs its hidden state which is then the input for the decoder as well as an arbitrary start state. The decoder then predicts the state of the first next time step and gets its new hidden state and the predicted output state as new input for predicting the second next time step. This process is then repeated for as many time steps as defined by the sequence length. The first state of this predicted sequence is then the last state of the next input sequence for the encoder and the old first state in the sequence is dropped. Therefore the sliding window of subsequent states is updated throughout this process. Using the multi-step approach yields the advantage, since the network's multi-step prediction is tested against the real sequence of states, that the prediction error is included in the prediction process itself and therefore in the learning process, therefore mitigating the prediction error in general [55].

4. Results and Discussion

In the following chapter the results of this project are presented and discussed.

4.1 Generation of Initial Trajectories

Before the neural network for environment modeling has been trained, the initial DRL algorithm for the 2D flow past a cylinder has been used to create a set of initial trajectories. In contrast to [14] the DRL algorithm was changed regarding the DRL control start time sampling as mentioned in Subsection 3.4.3. The start time has been randomly sampled from an interval between [2.5, 4.9] seconds of the simulation environment and the training has been conducted for 100 episodes with 80 iterations for the policy and value network updates. Furthermore, the seed of PyTorch’s internal random number generator has been set to zero in order to provide more reproducibility. The mean reward with its standard deviation vs. the episodes obtained by the agent during the training is plotted in Figure 4.1a.

(a) Mean reward and standard deviation of the initial DRL training over Episodes. (b) Mean rewards and standard deviations with different action sampling distributions of the initial DRL training over Episodes of the findings of [14]. Image source: Figure 5.8 [14].

Figure 4.1: Comparison of the rewards obtained by the initial DRL training conducted for this thesis and the findings of [14].

It can be seen that the reward starts at approximately -0.23 and in general continuously grows with a higher rate until episode 25 after which the gradient decreases and the mean reward is comparably stable at about -0.065 . A minor drop can be seen at episode 14, which corresponds to the increase of the drag at that episode. The general development of the reward is similar to the findings of [14] using the beta distribution, rising relatively fast at the beginning and reducing steepness from episode 24 onward. For a comparison, the reward obtained by the improvements made by [14] can be seen in Figure 4.1b. Figure 4.2a shows the mean c_D values per episode. At episode 35 a sudden drop in c_D can be observed, which resulted from ten failed trajectories during the DRL training at that episode, therefore the mean c_D represents only two trajectories.

(a) Mean and standard deviation of c_D per episode. The sudden drop in c_D resulted from ten failed trajectories during DRL training, therefore the bottom plot is zoomed to the relevant part of the plot. (b) Mean and standard deviation of c_L per episode

(c) Mean and standard deviation of ω_μ per episode

Figure 4.2: Means and standard deviations of different parameters of the initial DRL training per episode averaged over all trajectories of each episode.

The source seems to be a malfunction of the file handling system during that episode because the SLURM log-file showed the message “touch: finished.txt kann nicht beruehrt werden: Veraltetes Datei-Handle”. Since this has been a singular incident it is assumed to be a random malfunction. At the beginning of the training, the drag coefficient starts high at app. 3.175 and is on average continuously decreased until episode 25 which is synchronous to the increase in reward seen in Figure 4.1a. The DRL agent is able to properly control the flow in order to reduce the drag on the cylinder. The same applies to the lift coefficient, which can be seen in Figure 4.2b. The mean lift starts at about 0.0 and then decreases until reaching a global minimum at episode 30 of about -0.18 to increase back to a global maximum at episode 50 of about 0.06. The amplitude of the oscillation is decreased towards the end of the training. Figure 4.2c shows the mean and standard deviation of the mean ω_μ , which is the mean or mode of the beta distribution. The course of the mean ω_μ corresponds between episode ten to episode 50 to the course of the lift coefficient since its increase and decrease seem to be in-phase but anti proportional to the lift. Since the reward in general increased and the DRL agent was able to mitigate the drag and the fluctuations of the lift, the created initial trajectories are considered to be suitable and are used for further elaborations.

4.2 Environment Model Training

A feed-forward neural network has been implemented for predicting the pressure along the cylinder’s surface as well as the drag and the lift coefficient. The model has been trained without the DRL algorithm interfering by using the initially created set of trajectories where the DRL agent controls the flow. The trajectory data was normalized using min-max-scaling and split into sets of features and labels. The previous state is the feature and the next temporal state is the label.

The FFNN has been trained using only a few trajectories to prove the feasibility of time series prediction using an FFNN. As a next step, the input features have been extended with multiple subsequent temporal states also containing the pressure and rotational velocity values. For the purpose of reducing the required computational resources the state containing the 400 pressure values has been reduced.

Since the predicted state data is multivariate the given values for the MSE and MAE are uniformly averaged over the MSE and MAE for the whole state. The errors have been calculated on the normalized data, scaled to an interval between $[-1, 1]$.

4.2.1 FFNN Training

As a first step the environment model has been trained for 10000 epochs using 10000 randomly selected feature label pairs. Only one time step has been included in the feature vector and the complete pressure information of the cylinder’s surface has been included. To show the feasibility of time series prediction of the relevant environment information the model has first been tested in-sample, meaning that it had always access to the real pressure information produced by the simulation. Figure 4.3 exemplary shows the drag and lift coefficients for four randomly chosen test trajectories. The predicted c_D and c_L are depicted by the red dashed and orange dashed lines, respectively. The real drag and lift values are depicted by the black and blue curves, respectively. Figure 4.4 shows the relative prediction error for the pressure prediction as a heatmap.

The colour scale ranges from dark blue for low errors over green to yellow for high errors. The maximum relative prediction error for the values of the pressure sensors is approximately 0.49% for these four trajectories.

Since the predicted and real c_D and c_L curves fit almost perfectly it can be concluded that the FFNN architecture is in general capable of reproducing the drag and lift coefficients from a single previous time step as long as the model has access to the real values to predict from. The prediction data on the whole test set of 192 test trajectories of p , c_D and c_L is summarised in Table 4.1. The error values for the full state are similar to the values for the pressure since the data is averaged over the full state containing the 400 pressure values, c_D and c_L therefore the drag and the lift have a smaller influence on the error of the full state.

Parameter	MSE mean	MSE Standard deviation	MAE mean	MAE Standard deviation	MSE max	MAE max
Overall	1.3430e-05	6.2385e-06	0.002730	0.0005052	5.2881e-05	0.005421
p	1.3242e-05	6.2570e-06	0.002720	0.0005062	5.2691e-05	0.005412
c_D	1.7370e-05	0.0001263	0.002250	0.002226	0.001788	0.03243
c_L	8.4404e-05	1.7495e-05	0.007348	0.0007831	0.0001631	0.01010

Table 4.1: In-sample mean and maximum mean squared and mean absolute errors over full test set.

The previously presented results showed the general feasibility of the time-series prediction using a feed-forward neural network. The task of the neural network is to sample or predict whole trajectories from a few start states, therefore the model needs to be able to predict from its own predictions step by step.

Figure 4.3: c_D , c_L in-sample prediction (orange) and real (blue) values over the course of four unseen trajectories. Parameters: 50 neurons, 5 hidden layers, 1 time step.

Figure 4.4: In-sample relative prediction error for all 400 pressure sensors over the course of four different trajectories. The colours from blue to yellow indicate the size of the relative prediction error per sensor. Parameters: 50 neurons, 5 hidden layers, 1 time step.

This prediction technique is called autoregression since the model uses its own output predictions as the input for the next step. The model cannot predict whole trajectories at once since at deployment the DRL agent shall interact with the environment, therefore, changing it and the model prediction relies on the value of the chosen action by the DRL agent that it has chosen on the current state. Figure 4.5 shows the predicted (red, orange) and real (black, blue) values for the drag and lift coefficient for four randomly selected trajectories. The x-axis shows the dimensionless time steps and the y-axis the c_D or c_L values. The curves for the drag coefficient start really fast do diverge from the real values. Although the model seems to get the general decreasing direction of the curve, except for the third c_D plot from the top. Regarding the plots for the lift coefficient, the model seems to grasp the oscillatory behavior of the lift coefficient, however, it is not able to reconstruct the amplitude in most cases, therefore underpredicting the lift coefficient values. Only for approximately the first 20 time steps does the model correctly estimate the lift coefficient except for the third c_L plot from the top.

Figure 4.6 depicts the pressure value prediction for the four trajectories over the course of each whole trajectory. The x-axis shows the dimensionless time steps of the trajectory and the y-axis shows the number of the pressure sensor. The color bar on the right depicts the relative prediction error in percent. The maximum prediction error among the four trajectories is app. 15.4%. The evolution of the pressure error values over time follows an oscillatory behavior as well since the high error regions are followed by low error regions. Compared to the oscillation of the lift coefficient it can be seen that the frequency of the pressure prediction error oscillation is in phase with the oscillation of the lift coefficient. Since the maximum prediction errors occur mostly when the lift coefficient reaches a local maximum.

The prediction error data on the whole test set of 192 test trajectories of p , c_D and c_L is summarised in Table 4.2.

Parameter	MSE mean	MSE Standard deviation	MAE mean	MAE Standard deviation	MSE max	MAE max
Overall	0.009417	0.002248	0.07272	0.009006	0.01805	0.1039
p	0.008736	0.05150	0.3876	0.04925	0.01690	0.5608
c_D	0.08017	0.002082	0.07156	0.008879	0.4267	0.1024
c_L	0.2112	0.06897	0.2213	0.1001	0.4170	0.5609

Table 4.2: Autoregressive mean, standard deviation and maximum mean squared and mean absolute errors over full test set.

The comparison between the in-sample regressive and autoregressive results yields an increase in the mean MSE of the pressure, the drag and the lift coefficient of about $\Delta MSE_{p,mean} = 658\%$, $\Delta MSE_{c_D,mean} = 4614\%$ and $\Delta MSE_{c_L,mean} = 2501\%$ respectively. Therefore the current model is not able to predict whole trajectories by using only one previous time step.

Influence of Multiple Time Steps as Model Input

In order to increase the prediction accuracy, the model input has been extended by adding multiple subsequent states. Since a PyTorch neural network is natively not able to take in sequences of inputs the input feature dimension is extended by stacking the input vectors. Therefore if the input uses two subsequent steps the input dimension of the model is 802, for three steps 1203, etc.

Figure 4.7 depicts the model results on the whole test set for different time steps as boxplots. The x-axis of each plot shows the number of subsequent time steps used as model input and the y-axis shows the MSE or L_{max} prediction error. The results for the subsequent time steps of one, two, three, and four have been generated each using the full state of 400 pressure sensors. The training has only been conducted once per number of time steps.

Figure 4.5: c_D , c_L autoregressive prediction (orange) and real (blue) values over the course of four unseen trajectories. Parameters: 50 neurons, 5 hidden layers, 1 time step.

Figure 4.6: Autoregressive relative prediction error for all 400 pressure sensors over the course of four unssen trajectories. The colours from blue to yellow indicate the size of the relative prediction error per sensor. Parameters: 50 neurons, 5 hidden layers, 1 time step.

Figure 4.7: Comparison between MSE and L_{max} of models with different subsequent states.

The results for 20 and 30 steps are generated using only 16 pressure sensors. The discrepancy in the number pressure of sensors results from an error during the evaluation that has been detected rather late during the course of this project wherefore the number of subsequent states had to be increased more drastically. The dependencies on different numbers of pressure sensors are presented later in Subsection 4.2.1. The medians of the displayed quantity are depicted by solid orange lines. The mean is depicted by the green dashed line and outliers are depicted as red circles outside the whiskers. The box ranges from the first quartile (Q1) to the third quartile (Q3) of the underlying data and the whiskers range from the box edges further 1.5x of the interquartile range (IQR), which is the range from Q1 to Q3, and describe the most outlying data point that is not considered an outlier. Q1 describes that 25% of the smallest values are lower or equal than this value and Q3 describes that 75% of the values are smaller or equal than this value. The top left diagram shows the MSE distribution of the full state prediction, meaning pressure value prediction as well as c_D and c_L . The highest median can be observed for the model predictions using only one step, which is about 0.009286. The model error does not necessarily

Number of steps	Parameter	Median MSE	Median L_{max}	Parameter	Median MSE	Median L_{max}
1	Full state	0.009286	0.4675	p	7.9969e-05	0.1433
2	Full state	0.004851	0.7463	p	0.0002311	0.1019
3	Full state	0.003112	0.2913	p	0.0002871	0.09201
4	Full state	0.007324	0.7564	p	0.001184	0.1250
20	Full state	0.001113	0.1879	p	9.03864e-06	0.05311
30	Full state	0.0006774	0.1299	p	0.0001443	0.03990
1	c_D	0.02744	0.2557	c_L	0.1272	0.4675
2	c_D	0.5703	0.7463	c_L	0.0007221	0.2228
3	c_D	0.05664	0.2508	c_L	0.0002275	0.2829
4	c_D	0.8059	0.7564	c_L	0.001178	0.2694
20	c_D	0.006489	0.1228	c_L	3.2552e-05	0.1810
30	c_D	0.007038	0.1100	c_L	0.0001823	0.1184

Table 4.3: Medians of MSE and maximum error of full state, pressure, c_D and c_L prediction for models with different numbers of subsequent input steps. The data has been generated using the full test set.

decrease with an increasing number time steps, since the full state MSE for the four time step training is higher than for the two and three step models, although the 20 and 30 time step models yield the lowest full state MSE. This could result from a low number of parameters that the chosen model architecture includes too few parameters, since the number of hidden neurons is 50. Similar behavior can be observed for the pressure prediction error. The median MSE for the one step model is almost the lowest and for the four step model the highest. Although, for lower numbers of time steps the model error has a rather high variance, the expectation that higher numbers of time steps yield lower prediction errors can be met here. Looking at the L_{max} error, the 30 time step model yields the lowest maximum error for the full state, the drag, and the lift predictions. The exact error data is presented in Table 4.3.

The previous elaborations confirmed that the autoregressive prediction error, in general, seems to depend on the number of subsequent states included in the model input. But the presented data might suffer from high variance due to the model architecture. The low number of hidden neurons could lead to a low number of free parameters for the model to train and therefore higher errors even for higher numbers of time steps. The 20 and 30 step models showed the lowest median errors regarding all parameters. The 20 step model has regarding the MSE of the pressure and lift coefficient even lower median errors but the lowest median maximum errors are reached by the 30 step model and the overall lowest median MSE and maximum errors are also reached by the 30 step model. Therefore the 30 step approach is applied for the environment model.

Influence of the State Reduction

The increase of input features by including multiple subsequent states leads to an increase in memory consumption and processing power therefore the model state has been decreased to reduce the aforementioned problem. Table 4.4 shows the amount of memory consumption of a single state for single- and double-precision float arrays.

Number of sensors	Memory consumption single precision		Memory consumption double precision	
1	32 bits	4 bytes	64 bits	8 bytes
8	256 bits	32 bytes	512 bits	64 bytes
16	512 bits	64 bytes	1024 bits	128 bytes
25	800 bits	100 bytes	1600 bits	200 bytes
50	1600 bits	200 bytes	3200 bits	400 bytes
400	12800 bits	1600 bytes	25600 bits	3200 bytes

Table 4.4: Single and double precision memory consumption of the different numbers of pressure sensors in comparison.

It can be seen that the amount of memory consumed by the full state of 400 pressure sensors is about 1600 bytes for single precision and 3200 bytes for double precision. If the full state of 400 sensors plus the action and the drag and lift coefficients with single precision would be used for training, with 30 subsequent time steps, using the full train data consisting of feature-label pairs from 794 trajectories, which include 369 time steps, the memory consumption would result in about $((401 \cdot 4 \text{ bytes}) \cdot 30) + 402 \cdot 4 \cdot 369 \cdot 794 = 13.569 \text{ GiB}$. As mentioned in Subsection 3.5.7 the reduction of the state from 400 pressure values, each for one pressure sensor, has been investigated by uniformly reducing the state by keeping each 8th, 16th, 25th, and 50th pressure value. In order to investigate the performance different models with reduced states have been trained. In contrast to the in Subsection 4.2.1 chosen model using 30 steps each model used has 4 subsequent time steps since the lateness of the aforementioned error in the evaluation did not provide enough time and capacity to retrain the different models with 30 time steps and it is

Figure 4.8: Comparison between MSE and L_{max} of models with different numbers of pressure sensors as input for the environment model.

anticipated that the results would have been similar. The results for the different numbers of included pressure sensors are depicted in Figure 4.8 as boxplot.

The diagrams in Figure 4.8 depict the MSE and L_{max} distribution of the whole test set for different numbers of pressure sensors used for the model input. The x-axis of each plot shows the number of sensors and the y-axis shows the MSE and L_{max} prediction error. The training has only been conducted once per number of pressure sensors. The key components of the MSE and L_{max} error data presented in the plots are also summarised in Table 4.5.

Number of pressure sensors	Parameter	Median MSE	Median L_{max}	Parameter	Median MSE	Median L_{max}
8	Full state	0.004442	0.4194	p	0.0005711	0.09931
16	Full state	0.003775	0.3447	p	6.3308e-05	0.09958
25	Full state	0.008768	0.9964	p	0.001154	0.1536
50	Full state	0.002426	0.2765	p	0.0002159	0.08206
400	Full state	0.007324	0.7564	p	0.001184	0.1250
8	c_D	0.1534	0.4144	c_L	0.0005115	0.2569
16	c_D	0.09989	0.3308	c_L	0.001914	0.3070
25	c_D	1.0194	0.9964	c_L	0.0003723	0.2269
50	c_D	0.05103	0.2379	c_L	0.0004096	0.2461
400	c_D	0.8059	0.7564	c_L	0.001178	0.2694

Table 4.5: Medians of MSE and maximum error of full state, pressure, c_D and c_L prediction for models with different numbers of pressure sensors used for model input. The data has been generated using the full test set.

The 25 sensor model yielded, regarding MSE and L_{max} , the worst results, except for the prediction of the lift coefficient. The 50 sensor model yielded the best results regarding L_{max} and MSE, except for the MSE of the lift and pressure, where the 16 sensor model yielded better results. It was expected that prediction accuracy would have decreased by reducing the number of pressure sensors but this is not necessarily true, since the 400 sensor model did not yield always better results than the other models. The increase of prediction accuracy of lower numbers of pressure

sensors might result from the reduced complexity of the neural network since it means that the number of input neurons and therefore the number of weighted neuron-neuron connections is decreased. Therefore the number of parameters for the network to learn is also decreased, which reduces the complexity of the learning process. Furthermore, the higher prediction errors for the 8 and 25 sensor models in contrast to the 16 and 50 sensor models lead to the conclusion that the placement of the pressure sensors used for the prediction does influence the outcome. Considering the current results, the assumption that fewer numbers of pressure sensors yield even better results regarding the MSE could be made, although the data might have high variance due to the low number of neurons per hidden layer. The variance could also result from the fact that each training has only been conducted once and the training outcome is not deterministic.

Since the 16 sensor model is the second best model regarding the error, after the 50 sensor model, and the memory consumption of a 16 sensor state (0.9954 GiB) is lower than that of a 50 sensor state (2.1086 GiB), the chosen number of pressure sensors used for the environment model input is 16 for the further elaborations.

Error Accumulation of Autoregressive Predictions

The purpose of the environment model is to conduct autoregressive time series prediction, therefore after reaching the n th prediction step, with n being the number of subsequent steps used for the model input, further predictions only rely on previous predictions by the model without having any access to the initial start state anymore. The autoregressive predictions, therefore, lead to an accumulating prediction error, since the prediction error of the previous prediction is also included in the prediction process of the next time step. This behavior can be seen in Figure 4.9, which exemplarily shows the values for the real and predicted drag and lift coefficients over the course of four different trajectories with 369 predicted steps. The x-axis denotes the dimensionless time t^* and the y-axis the values of the drag and lift, respectively. The course of the predicted drag coefficients for the, from the top, third and fourth trajectory starts to diverge from the real values as the trajectory is predicted further into the future. The same behaviour, although not as much as regarding the drag, can be seen for the lift coefficient. It is more severe for the bottom trajectory, which starts to get out of phase by app. $t^* = 50$.

The same applies for the pressure prediction error per sensor over time, which is depicted in Figure 4.10 as a heatmap. The maximum prediction errors for the four trajectories are reached at later instances in time. For example for the bottom right plot at app. $t^* = 62.0$ with an error of about 5.8%.

Figure 4.11 shows the MSE and the L_{max} prediction error of each prediction over time for the four different trajectories. The MSE of the first trajectory from the top shows the highest error and fluctuation at earlier time steps at about $t^* = 52.5$ and following and the second trajectory from the top shows high error fluctuations at earlier time steps but also at later steps in time at $t^* = 61.0$ and following. The MSE for the third and fourth plot from the top (blue) shows that the highest prediction errors are made during later predictions reaching their maximum at app. $t^* = 45.0$ and $t^* = 57.5$, being 0.00052 and 0.001, respectively. Especially the L_{max} error shows the deterioration of the prediction error towards later time steps. For all trajectories, the maximum error starts in early stages to oscillate upwards always increasing the mean maximum error. The decrease of the model prediction error towards later time steps has been expected, due to the error accumulation of autoregressive prediction.

As a consequence of the error accumulation and the deterioration of the prediction accuracy the model is used to only predict 200 time steps ahead which represents a time span of $t = 1$ s and a dimensionless time span of $\Delta t^* = 10$.

Figure 4.9: Autoregressive predicted and real c_D and c_L coefficients per step of four different random trajectories.

Figure 4.10: Heatmaps of the relative autoregressive prediction error per sensor of four different random trajectories.

Figure 4.11: MSE and L_{max} prediction error per step of four different random trajectories.

4.2.2 LSTM Training

Two different LSTM architecture approaches have been tested: Single-step and multi-step prediction. Training and testing the two LSTM architectures have only been conducted briefly due to low performance with the initial architectures and limited time for further elaboration of the approach. The architectures with variations of only a few different parameters have therefore only been tested for prediction on a random spot sample of the trajectories and not on the whole test set.

Single-step Prediction

For the single-step prediction the LSTM has been trained varying the number of fully connected hidden layers in a range of $[1, 2, 3, 4, 5]$ containing 128 neurons each. The learning rate has been fixed to $\eta = 0.001$, the batch size is 64, the state features have been reduced to 16 pressure sensors plus the action for each step, and 30 subsequent states are used for the prediction of the next state. The one-layer model has been trained for 1000 epochs and the two-, three-, four-, and five-layer models have been trained for 100 epochs each. Figure 4.12 shows the real and predicted values for c_D and c_L , the relative prediction error of the pressure values of each of the 400 sensors. The training has been conducted for 1000 epochs. For the first few time steps up until app. $t^* = 33.75$, the curves of the predicted and real drag and lift coefficients are fitting well. Predicting further into the future the predicted c_D starts to diverge from the real values. The number of training epochs is low, therefore, longer training times might increase the accuracy. Furthermore, the model does only have one hidden layer, which means the parameters space to be adjusted during learning is also small. The oscillating behavior of the lift coefficient can still be captured but the amplitude of the predicted lift diverges from the real values as the prediction gets further into the future. Figure 4.12b depicts the relative prediction error of the pressure values per sensor. The maximum prediction error for this trajectory is 11.69%. An upward oscillating behavior for predictions further into the future can be observed here, too.

Figure 4.12: (a) c_D , c_L prediction and real values over the course of a single trajectory. (b) Relative prediction error for all 400 pressure sensors over the course of a single trajectory. The colours from blue to yellow indicate the size of the relative prediction error per sensor. Parameters: 128 neurons, 1 hidden layer.

Figure 4.13: (a) c_D , c_L prediction and real values over the course of a single trajectory. (b) Relative prediction error for all 400 pressure sensors over the course of a single trajectory. The colours from blue to yellow indicate the size of the relative prediction error per sensor. Parameters: 128 neurons, 5 hidden layers.

Figure 4.13 depicts the same plotting as for Figure 4.12 but for a network with five hidden layers and trained for only 100 epochs. The values for the predicted drag coefficient are also diverging after about 40 time steps. The drag coefficient is predicted too high with $MAE_{c_D} = 0.1371$ and $MSE_{c_D} = 0.02097$. The predicted lift coefficient somehow reconstructs an oscillating behaviour but it gets out of phase at about $t^* = 48.5$. Figure 4.13b shows the relative prediction error for the pressure sensors. The maximum relative pressure prediction error is about 12.38% which is even higher than for the LSTM with one hidden layer. Similar to the results from the one layer LSTM the prediction error gets worse the further the model predicts into the future which probably also results from the accumulating error as the model predicts from its predictions.

The presented results only depict a snapshot of the performance for a single trajectory and for a limited parameter space. A final profound conclusion for the performance of a single-step LSTM can therefore not be made here. Although it becomes clear that the model performance decreases the further the model predicts into the future which probably results from the accumulation of the prediction error throughout the prediction process. Training the model autoregressively might mitigate this problem. The plotted results for the two-, three-, and four-layer single-step LSTM can be found in Appendix A. These training results are similar to the ones presented.

4.2.3 Multi-step Prediction

As mentioned in Subsection 3.5.9 the purpose of the multi-step LSTM is to predict the states of multiple time steps ahead from multiple time steps before, also called sequence-to-sequence prediction. The sequence to predict from is now denoted with feature sequence. Since the DRL agent still has to interact with the environment at each predicted time step, not the full predicted sequence of states is used but only the first time step from the predicted sequence. The first step is then added to the next feature sequence dropping the first step in order to move the sliding window. This approach might include longer prediction horizons by comparing against a sequence of labels, therefore minimizing the prediction error. The approach has only been tested briefly by training different hyperparameter combinations for multi-step LSTMs. The different combinations can be seen in Table 4.6. Each model has been trained for 10000 epochs, using a learning rate of 0.0001, and 16 pressure sensors per input state.

Number of hidden layers	Batch size	Feature sequence length	Prediction sequence length	Number of hidden layers	Batch size	Feature sequence length	Prediction sequence length
1	64	10	5	1	128	10	5
1	64	20	10	1	256	10	5
1	64	20	20	1	256	20	5
1	64	20	30	1	256	30	5
1	64	30	10	1	256	40	5
1	64	30	20	1	512	10	5
1	64	30	30	2	256	50	5
1	64	40	10	3	256	10	5
1	64	40	20	4	256	10	5
1	128	10	5	5	256	10	5

Table 4.6: Different parameter combinations of hyperparameters used for multi-step LSTM

Each of the in Table 4.6 depicted hyperparameter combinations has shown severe cases of overfitting after 1000 to 2000 training epochs, which can be seen in the example of the 1 layer network with a feature sequence length of 10 predicting a sequence length of 5 in Figure 4.14. The x-axis shows the number of epochs and the y-axis the MSE loss. The train loss is depicted in blue and the validation loss is depicted in orange.

Overfitting in the context of DL describes the phenomenon of a neural network starting to memorize the seen training samples and some underlying pattern, therefore decreasing or losing

Figure 4.14: Exemplary training and validation loss of a tested multi-layer LSTM. Parameters: 50 hidden neurons, 1 hidden layer, batch size 64, feature sequence length: 10, prediction sequence length: 5.

Figure 4.15: Predicted and real c_D and c_L plotted for five different test trajectories of a tested multi-layer LSTM. Parameters: 50 hidden neurons, 1 hidden layer, batch size 64, feature sequence length: 10, prediction sequence length: 5.

its generalization capabilities [58]. It can be recognized by the increasing discrepancy between the training and validation loss. The train loss keeps improving while the validation loss starts to stay on the same level or even increases. Figure 4.14 depicts this behavior very well. The same phenomenon has been observed for the other combinations.

The low prediction capabilities can be seen in Figure 4.15. The predicted drag and lift are depicted by the red and orange dashed lines and the real drag and lift are depicted by the black and blue solid lines, respectively. The predicted and real drag and lift coefficients diverge directly at the beginning of the trajectory. The drag drops instantly from about 3.0 at the beginning to app. 2.1. The predicted lift stays with some noisy variations around a value of 0.2 for each trajectory.

The variations of the hyperparameters did not yield any better results which might result from an error in the implementation but also from the severe cases of overfitting which can be observed for each of the different hyperparameter combinations. Overfitting can in general be tackled by implementing an early stopping strategy but due to time constraints and since the current results yield no further insights, the approach has not been pursued further. The results for the different combinations are attached in Appendix B but are not presented in detail here, since the approach has been dropped.

4.3 Integration Into the PPO Algorithm

After the model training has been conducted, the environment model has been deployed for use with the DRL algorithm. In order to integrate trajectory sampling from the environment model into the DRL algorithm the replay buffer function has to be adapted. As mentioned in Subsection 3.4.2 the replay buffer is used to store past experiences generated using the current policy π_k . The policy and value network are then trained using the experiences from the replay buffer. The regular DRL algorithm samples its experiences from the trajectories generated using the simulation of OpenFOAM. The model-based approach presented here, therefore, replaces the simulation with the environment model by filling the replay buffer using the output of the environment model. There are two possible deployment scenarios that are planned for this thesis. The first approach is to train the DRL algorithm using only the environment model and the second approach is to mix DRL training using the environment model and the simulation of OpenFOAM.

4.3.1 Model-based Sampling

The model-based sampling of the environment is conducted using the environment model with 5 hidden layers, 50 neurons per hidden layer, 30 subsequent states, a state reduction of 16 pressure values per state, trained for 10000 epochs on app. 10000 feature-label pairs. The parameters are summarised in Table 4.7.

Parameter	Value
Learning rate	0.0001
Batch Size	256
Number of epochs	10000
Neurons per hidden layer	50
Number of hidden layers	5
Number of training samples	10000
Number of pressure sensors	16
Number of subsequent states to predict from	30

Table 4.7: Parameters of the first model-based DRL training using only the environment model.

In order to apply model-based sampling of trajectories to the DRL algorithm the process of filling the replay buffer has to be adapted. As mentioned in Subsection 3.4.2, training the DRL agent using the simulation environment is conducted by using an initial policy and letting the agent control 10 different environments in parallel with it. The policy and value networks are then updated using the replay buffer filled with the previously gathered experience tuples from the different environments. The model-based sampling of trajectories replaces the simulation by using the environment model. Therefore an initial sequence of states for the environment model to predict from has to be set. At first 10000 randomly selected sequences of states are sampled from the pool of initial trajectories. At runtime ten random start sequences are then selected and the environment model is autoregressively used to predict the next 200 subsequent states containing the values of the pressure, c_D , and c_L coefficients. Each trajectory is sampled sequentially and not in parallel, like the ten different simulation environments. After a full trajectory is sampled, the rewards and returns, and the log probabilities for the trajectory are computed and the replay buffer is filled with the states, actions, rewards, returns and log probabilities for the trajectory. Repeated for each of the ten trajectories, the buffer is filled step-by-step. After all trajectories of a single episode are finished and the buffer is filled, the data is saved to the disk. A depiction of the algorithm can be seen in Figure 4.16.

Figure 4.16: Flow chart of model-based trajectory sampling and filling of the replay buffer.

Since the DRL training turned out to not always be stable, the model-based DRL training has been conducted with eleven different seeds used for the random number generator. Figure 4.17 shows the results of the mean reward per episode of all different seeds and the reward of the initial DRL training using the simulation environment in comparison. The x-axis shows the number of episodes and the y-axis the mean reward and standard deviation, respectively.

The mean rewards per episode for the DRL training conducted using the simulation is depicted by the light red dashed line. The calculated rewards for the different trajectories look very chaotic. Many seeds resulted in a diverging DRL training process creating large drops in the reward to about -0.55 or -0.65 , i.e. seeds 2, 5 and 9, which are depicted by the dotted red, dashed yellow, and dashed-dotted green graphs. The standard deviations for the different seeds mainly follow the same pattern. There are some seeds, i.e. seeds 0, 1 or 10 which are depicted by the solid blue, dotted green and brown solid line, that generated rewards in the magnitude of the simulation reward of approximately -0.065 . This level is reached by the simulation reward after about 25 episodes. It stands out the mean reward for each seed already starts at approximately the same high level of mean reward, whereas the simulation mean reward starts at a low level of approximately -0.25 . Figure 4.18 depicts the mean drag coefficient and its standard deviation vs. episodes for the 11 seeds and the simulation DRL training, averaged over all trajectories of an episode. The diverging reward might result from a low prediction accuracy of the model.

Similar to the mean reward of two, five, and nine the mean c_D per episode diverges significantly from the simulation drag. It stands out that the mean drag per episode for each seed in the first episodes does not match the simulation drag. It seems that the predicted drag coefficients are on average smaller in the beginning than it is the case for the simulation. The standard deviation of the mean drag of the seeds is slightly higher in the beginning and starts on average to increase towards later episodes. Especially seed six yields the highest maximum standard deviation of approximately 0.5. Figure 4.19 shows the mean lift coefficient averaged over all trajectories per episode for the eleven different seeds and the simulation.

The already identified outlier seeds are also showing the highest deviations from the simulation regarding the mean lift coefficient per episode. The general trend of the seeds to start at a different level of drag does not apply to the lift and the standard deviation of the lift coefficient, although a general increasing trend of the standard deviations towards later episodes can be observed. Another parameter to investigate the divergence of the model-based DRL training is the mean angular velocity. Figure 4.20 shows the mean of the mean angular velocities per episode. Furthermore, the standard deviation of the mean angular velocity averaged per episode is plotted.

Here also the identified outlier seeds are diverging from the average mean angular velocity per episode of the simulation. The same applies to the standard deviation, although the general increasing trend can be seen towards later episodes, too.

In order to investigate the already high rewards generated by the model-based training, the environment model predictions of c_D and c_L have been tested against the data from the initial simulation DRL training per trajectory per episode. Therefore the model has been given the initial 30 state sequence from the beginning of five different randomly selected trajectories per episode. The model predicted each trajectory autoregressively and the MSE and MAE have been calculated for each trajectory. The data is depicted in Figure 4.21.

The x-axis depicts the number of episodes and the y-axis depicts the MSE and MAE, respectively. On the left side, depicted in blue, the MAE and MSE for the drag coefficient can be seen. It can be seen that the MSE and MAE on average for the first episodes up until episode 25 start at a higher level and follow a decreasing trend until starting to increase again until later episodes. There is one outlier in episode 14 with $MAE = 0.35$ and $MSE = 0.19$. The MAE and MSE for the lift coefficient are depicted on the right side in orange.

Figure 4.17: Mean reward and standard deviation per episode of 11 differently seeded model-based DRL trainings in comparison to the reward of the initial DRL training conducted with the simulation. Parameters: 50 neurons, 5 layers

Figure 4.18: Mean drag coefficient and standard deviation per episode of 11 differently seeded model-based DRL trainings in comparison to the reward of the initial DRL training conducted with the simulation. Parameters: 50 neurons, 5 layers

Figure 4.19: Mean lift coefficient and standard deviation per episode of eleven differently seeded model-based DRL trainings in comparison to the reward of the initial DRL training conducted with the simulation. Parameters: 50 neurons, 5 layers

Figure 4.20: Average mean angular velocity and standard deviation per episode of 11 differently seeded model-based DRL trainings in comparison to the reward of the initial DRL training conducted with the simulation. Parameters: 50 neurons, 5 layers

Figure 4.21: MSE and MAE of autoregressive trajectory predictions tested per episode of the initial simulation DRL training.

A similar trend cannot be observed for the lift coefficient, since the c_L values are almost uniformly distributed in a band between 0.01 and 0.06 for the MAE and 0 and 0.01 for the MSE. The mean MSE is somewhere around 0.03. Only the lower limit of the MSE for the first about 10 episodes is slightly higher and decreases then for the other episodes. Furthermore, there are more outliers yielding higher MAEs and MSEs of up to 0.20 and 0.06, respectively.

As mentioned before, the reward of the model-based DRL training is already too high in the beginning. The same applies to the predicted drag coefficient c_D . Furthermore, the model predictions per episode of the initial DRL simulation training show higher error values, especially at the beginning of the training. This leads to the conclusion that the trained model may not be able to predict “bad” trajectories, meaning trajectories that were generated while the agent has not yet uncovered a control policy, that reduces the drag and therefore increases the reward properly. Figure 4.1a already showed that the reward of the DRL training mostly increased until episode 25 and does not increase much afterward until reaching a stable level at about -0.065 . Therefore the DRL agent already learned a “good” control strategy early and the episodes after episode 25 do have lower variance in their trajectory data. Since the model has been trained with 10000 training samples, which have been randomly selected from the train set containing the 80% of the initial trajectory data. And it is assumed that the later episodes, which are the greater part of the overall training data, do have lower variance and already yield higher rewards, than the episodes in the beginning, the variance in the selected 10000 training samples is also lower. This imbalance in the training data might lead to the already high rewards that the model-based DRL yields. In order to rule out this source of error the model has therefore been retrained with the trajectory data from the first 25 episodes to include higher variance data in the training process.

Retraining the Environment Model

The prediction performance of the retrained model regarding the initial trajectories similar to Figure 4.21, are depicted in Figure 4.22.

Figure 4.22: MSE and MAE of autoregressive trajectory predictions of the retrained environment model, tested per episode of the initial simulation DRL training.

Figure 4.23: MSE and MAE of autoregressive pressure predictions per trajectory of the pre-trained and retrained environment model, tested per episode of the initial simulation DRL training.

As before the x-axis shows the episode number and the y-axis the MAE and MSE, respectively. MAE and MSE for the drag coefficient are depicted on the left in blue and for the lift coefficient are depicted on the left in orange. It can be seen that the MAE scale of the drag, before being distributed narrowly in an interval between 0.0 and 0.25, now is more loosely distributed over a range of 0.0 to up to 1.5.

The same applies for the MSE of the drag. This is surprising since the model has been retrained using only the first 25 episodes, which show different general behavior than the rest, but the model prediction accuracy has been assumed to increase at least at the beginning. The prediction errors are distributed more uniformly between 0.0 and 1.0. Also, there seem to be more outliers above an MSE of 1.0 than before. The MAEs of the lift coefficient decreased for the first episodes after the retraining of the model. The mean MAE over the episodes has decreased on average until about episode 25 and is then again more or less stable around 0.05, which is slightly higher than before retraining. This could partly be explained by the fact that the first episodes contain different trajectory data than the later episodes. A similar increase, although not as drastic, can be seen regarding the mean pressure prediction per trajectory per episode which is depicted in Figure 4.23. The results of the retraining showed extreme divergence towards the average reward, the average drag and lift coefficient, and average mean omega per episode, therefore the retraining has not produced the expected increase of the prediction accuracy.

In order to investigate the cause of the training divergence ω_μ , c_D , c_L and the mean reward of the trajectories produced by the environment model at deployment have been plotted over the time steps. Figure 4.24 shows the trajectories of episode 1 of a model-based DRL training run.

Figure 4.24: ω_μ , c_D , c_L and reward for the predicted time steps of episode 1 of a model-based DRL training using the retrained model. The dashed red line marks the start of the prediction. Parameters: 50 neurons, 5 layers

The x-axis depicts the number of time steps and the y-axis ω_μ , c_D , c_L , and the reward. The dashed red line at time step 30 marks the start of the environment model predictions, all data before depicts the data of the 30 start states.

Figure 4.25: ω_μ , c_D , c_L and reward for the predicted time steps of episode 8 of a model-based DRL training using the retrained model. The dashed red line marks the start of the prediction. Parameters: 50 neurons, 5 layers

Figure 4.26: ω_μ , c_D , c_L and reward for the predicted time steps of episode 45 of a model-based DRL training using the retrained model. The dashed red line marks the start of the prediction. Parameters: 50 neurons, 5 layers

It can be seen that directly in the first episode one trajectory, namely trajectory 2, shows a high divergence of ω_μ towards the end, and therefore also the drag and the lift coefficient diverge. This also results in a very low reward of about -1400 . Figure 4.25 shows the trajectories of episode 8 of a model-based DRL training run with the retrained model.

In contrast, episode 8 contains no completely diverging trajectories, although all c_D values are increasing towards the end of the trajectories. The same applies for the lift coefficient, therefore the reward is reduced towards the end. The courses of ω_μ show some oscillatory behavior therefore the agent is somehow exploring different actions, but towards the end of the trajectories, the oscillations are reducing. The general course of the predicted c_D and c_L show in general realistic values. Therefore the environment model predictions do not always diverge but show in general plausible behavior. The divergence can also be seen for later episodes, as can exemplarily be seen in Figure 4.26. Here, about 2 trajectories diverge greatly, although ω_μ is showing convergence towards 0.0 for multiple trajectories. The resulting reward is even lower than in the first episode, resulting in approximately -60000 .

Since the courses of ω_μ somehow diverge and converge and still result in very low rewards, it seems that the action in general does not affect the prediction outcome of the environment model very much.

Because not all trajectories are diverging, the trajectory sampling is extended by dropping trajectories that show diverging behavior by introducing a minimal mean reward threshold of -0.5 per trajectory. All trajectories that produce a mean reward lower than this threshold are dropped and a new trajectory is sampled until the reward is greater than the threshold. Furthermore, the starting states are changed to a single starting state sampled from an uncontrolled 2D flow past a cylinder, that is used for all predicted trajectories. Since the previously randomly selected start states are sampled from all available trajectories, they contain pressures and ω_μ data that result from already controlled trajectories, yielding already high rewards and therefore low c_D values. In the simulation the DRL agent starts to control the flow when the formation of the vortex street has almost completely finished, therefore the prediction using the environment model should represent this flow behavior as well. The graphs of the drag and lift coefficient for the uncontrolled flow can be seen in Figure 4.27.

It can be seen that the average, minimum, and maximum drag are about $\bar{c}_D = 3.1941$, $c_{D_{max}} = 3.2240$, and $c_{D_{min}} = 3.1639$. The average, minimum and maximum lift are $\bar{c}_L = 0,0601$, $c_{L_{max}} = 0.9682$, and $c_{L_{min}} = -1.0045$. The values are similar to the data of Table 5.1 on page 29 from [14]. As can be seen in Figure 4.2a and elaborated in [14], the drag of the uncontrolled flow is about 5.05% higher than drag of the controlled flow. The single uncontrolled start state is randomly selected from the uncontrolled trajectory. ω_μ , c_D , c_L for the different trajectories of episode 0 using the uncontrolled initial start state can be seen in Figure 4.28.

It can be seen that no extremely diverging trajectory is sampled in episode 0. Furthermore, the trajectories look all really similar which, considering the same start state, is not surprising. ω_μ shows a weak oscillating behavior around -0.075 with an oscillation period of $\Delta t^* = 5$. The minimum and maximum ω_μ are approximately -0.10 and -0.05 , respectively. The drag starts slowly diverging towards the end of each trajectory with a maximum drag of about $c_{D_{max}} = 3.45$. The course of the lift coefficient for the different trajectories oscillates with the frequency of the uncontrolled flow. No changes in the behavior can be observed here. Since the drag is diverging towards the end, the reward is also diverging towards the end, although staying in a reasonable order of magnitude compared to the DRL training conducted with the simulation and the diverging rewards before. Figure 4.29 depicts the same plot as before only for episode 8 of the model-based DRL training.

Figure 4.27: c_D and c_L of the uncontrolled flow.

Figure 4.28: ω_μ , c_D , c_L and reward for the predicted time steps of episode 1 of a model-based DRL training using always the same start state from the uncontrolled flow and dropping trajectories yielding a mean reward < -0.5 . The dashed red line marks the start of the prediction. Parameters: 50 neurons, 5 layers

Figure 4.29: ω_μ , c_D , c_L and reward for the predicted time steps of episode 8 of a model-based DRL training using always the same start state from the uncontrolled flow and dropping trajectories yielding a mean reward < -0.5 . The dashed red line marks the start of the prediction. Parameters: 50 neurons, 5 layers

Figure 4.30: ω_μ , c_D , c_L and reward for the predicted time steps of episode 36 of a model-based DRL training using always the same start state from the uncontrolled flow and dropping trajectories yielding a mean reward < -0.5 . The dashed red line marks the start of the prediction. Parameters: 50 neurons, 5 layers

It stands out that the courses of the drag and the lift coefficient, as well as the reward, do not really differ from the data of episode 1 presented in Figure 4.28. Only the oscillatory behaviour and magnitude of ω_μ have changed.

After reaching the oscillation amplitude another oscillation amplitude right after the first can be observed. Furthermore the magnitude of ω_μ has increased now ranging from -2.2 to 2.0 , while the maximum drag stays at about $c_{D_{max}} = 3.45$. In Figure 4.30 ω_μ , c_D , c_L and the reward for episode 36 are shown. It can be seen that ω_μ is diverging after $t^* = 57$, yielding approximately $\omega_\mu = 7.5$. The general course of c_D and c_L is slightly different, with a deterioration towards later time steps. Therefore the reward also starts to diverge. This behavior might result from the environment model being confronted with values for ω_μ that are not much included in the train data, therefore the model has to extrapolate and the training diverges. It is striking that, although the courses of ω_μ for episodes 0, 8, and 35 are showing different behavior regarding the magnitude and the oscillatory behavior, the values for the drag and lift are not much being influenced. Only for ω_μ values towards the edges of the action space, do drag and lift deteriorate further. This behaviour leads to the conclusion that the action, that is part of the model input, does not influence the model output, therefore c_D and c_L , sufficiently. Another point that should be mentioned is, that the training has been stopped early at episode 35 since the more the training progressed, the more trajectories have been dropped. This led to a point where the training was caught in an almost endless generation of trajectories, therefore it has not been useful to let this training run any further.

As a conclusion, it is possible that the chosen model architecture is not sufficient to conduct a successful DRL training. Therefore two models containing 128 and 256 neurons per hidden layer have been trained additionally. Furthermore, another model using 256 neurons with a changed loss function has been implemented and trained. Since an implementation of different input weighting ω_μ would require more and complex adaptations of the implementation of the environment model, this approach could not be conducted, considering the late stage of this project.

Increased Number of Hidden Neurons

In order to improve the prediction accuracy of the environment model, the number of hidden neurons has been extended to 128 and 256 and the model has been deployed for use with the DRL algorithm. Figure 4.31 shows the mean reward per episode of the simulation DRL training and the model-based DRL training for 128 and 256 neurons.

It can be seen that the mean reward per episode for the 128 and 256 neuron model starts at a similar reward to the simulation training and increases for the first few episodes. As the training continues the mean reward for the 128 model first decreases until approximately episode 50 and then increases again. The mean reward of the 256 neuron model is first increasing a little bit until episode 17 and then decreases continuously. The same applies for the standard deviation of the mean rewards for both models. Furthermore the mean reward for the 256 neuron model is higher than the results for the 128 neuron model. Figure 4.32 depicts the mean drag per episode of the simulation and the model-based training runs.

Similar to the increase of the mean reward for the first few episodes the mean c_D per episode also decreases but then follows an increasing trend. The mean c_D for the 128 neuron model first increases with two sudden peaks in between until episode 50 and then decreases again. Regarding the 256 neuron model, c_D shows first a decreasing behavior until episode 22 and then increases, with a small peak at episode 54, further until the later episodes. The standard deviation of the mean drag for the two models follows the general course of the simulation and stays at a low level. The mean lift per episode is presented in Figure 4.33.

Figure 4.31: Mean reward per episode of the simulation and the model-based DRL training for the 128 and 256 neuron environment models.

Figure 4.32: Mean drag per episode of the simulation and the model-based DRL training for the 128 and 256 neuron environment models.

Figure 4.33: Mean lift per episode of the simulation and the model-based DRL training for the 128 and 256 neuron environment models.

Figure 4.34: Mean omega mean per episode of the simulation and the model-based DRL training for the 128 and 256 neuron environment models.

The lift for both models is decreasing towards episode 30 and then quickly increases for the 128 neuron model to 0.3 and suddenly drops for the 256 neuron model to -1.25 . They both more or less diverge from the mean lift that is produced by the simulation training, which on averages stays around 0.0. Both models show a small increase in the lift values towards later episodes. The standard deviation of the two models is more less similarly oscillating and has the same magnitudes as the simulation training for about 22 episodes after that the standard deviation drops to -0.01 , while the simulation training stays on average at approximately 0.075.

The standard deviation of the 256 neuron model starts to increase again from episode 70 towards the end. Figure 4.34 shows the average ω_μ for the model-based and simulation DRL training.

It can be seen that the mean action per episode shows an anti-proportional behavior compared to the lift. The courses of the mean ω_μ are at the beginning slightly higher than the ω_μ of the simulation DRL training until episode 25 for the 128 neuron model and until episode 32 for the 256 neuron model. After that, mean ω_μ of the 128 neuron model peaks at episode 30 to $6.0 \frac{rad}{s}$ and then drops to $-4.0 \frac{rad}{s}$. As the episodes progress mean ω_μ decreases further. The 256 neuron model increases to $7.4 \frac{rad}{s}$ staying there but decreasing a little bit towards the end. The standard deviation of ω_μ follows the same course as the standard deviation of the mean lift, therefore starting similar to the simulation DRL results and then decreases to about 0.01 and stays there. Only the standard deviation for the 256 neuron model increases towards the end again.

The comparison between the model-based DRL training results of the 128 and the 256 neuron model and the simulation DRL training, shows that the training, in the beginning, shows promising results but it diverges towards later episodes. Therefore just increasing the number of hidden neurons does not necessarily work, although the mean rewards of the 256 neuron model is on average higher than the mean reward for the 128 neuron model. Further increasing the number of neurons per hidden layer might lead to even better results. A comparison of the MSE and L_{max} prediction error performance on the test set is later elaborated at Figure 4.39

Results of the Weighted loss function

The weighted loss function is basically an adaption of the regular MSE loss function that weights the different parts of the model output differently. Since it seems that ω_μ does not have much effect on the outcome of the model, the model output is adapted to weigh c_D and c_L prediction similarly to the pressure prediction. Therefore all pressure sensors are considered as one unit and the drag and lift coefficients together are considered as one unit.

The weighting is implemented simply by multiplying a weight vector \mathbf{W} , having the same dimension as the prediction vector, with the prediction error vector before the mean of the squared prediction error is calculated. The formula looks as follows:

$$MSE_{weighted} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N (\mathbf{y}^* - \mathbf{y})^2 \cdot \mathbf{W} \quad (4.1)$$

The weighting factor of each pressure value is $\frac{2}{402} = N_c / (N_p + N_c)$ and the weighting for the coefficients is $\frac{400}{402} = N_p / (N_p + N_c)$. With $N_c = 2$ being the number of coefficients and $N_p = 400$ being the number of pressure sensors of the model output. This adaption might lead to a more balanced weighting of the output variables. It is important to note that the weighting is only applied to the output. The input still contains only the information of 16 pressure sensors per time step. For the training, a model architecture containing 5 hidden layers and 256 neurons per layer with a learning rate of 0.0001 and a batch size of 10000 is used. The model has been trained on the data of the first 40 episodes of the initial DRL training.

After training the weighted model has been deployed for use with the DRL algorithm. Therefore the DRL training has been conducted six times with six different seeds.

Figure 4.35: Mean reward per episode of the simulation and five differently seeded model-based DRL trainings using the environment model that has been trained with the weighted MSE loss. Parameter: 5 hidden layers, 256 neurons

Figure 4.36: Mean drag coefficient per episode of the simulation and the five differently seeded model-based DRL trainings using the environment model that has been trained with the weighted MSE loss. Parameter: 5 hidden layers, 256 neurons

The results of seed 4 have been skipped, since not the full training data could have been saved during training. The mean reward and standard deviation per episode of the different seeds in comparison with the simulation DRL training results can be seen in Figure 4.35. It can be seen that different seeds produce different DRL training results. This could already be observed in Figure 4.17. The mean reward for all seeds starts at a similar value as the simulation DRL training results, around -0.28 , and increases for a few episodes afterward.

Although showing a drop at episode 11, seed 2 and 5 show the highest mean rewards which is preserved towards the end of the training, which is about -0.20 . The seeds 0, 1 and 3 yield lower mean rewards per episode, although the mean reward of seed 1 increases after episode 48 towards -0.20 . Seed 0 suddenly increases at episode 38 to slowly degrade towards the end at -0.28 . Seed 3 decreases towards episode 60 to -0.31 and increases towards the end, reaching the roughly the same mean reward as seed 0.

Although the training has been conducted using the trajectory dropping mechanism with a threshold of -0.5 , there have not been many trajectories dropped during model-based DRL training and all 100 episodes could be computed. This leads to the conclusion that the weighting of the lift and drag coefficient might stabilize the prediction process in general.

The standard deviation of the mean reward for the seeds decreases for ten episodes and increases after that. Since a good mean reward is not the only measure of training quality the mean drag coefficient per episode is depicted in Figure 4.36, the mean lift coefficient per episode is depicted in Figure 4.37, and the mean ω_μ per episode is depicted in Figure 4.38.

Figure 4.37: Mean lift coefficient per episode of the simulation and the five differently seeded model-based DRL trainings using the environment model that has been trained with the weighted MSE loss. Parameter: 5 hidden layers, 256 neurons

The stable mean reward per episode of seed two and five results from the course of the drag coefficient, which shows a decrease at the beginning with a peak at episode 21 and a sudden drop afterward until decreasing more slowly towards the end of the training for the two seeds. The seeds zero, one, and three first also show a decrease until episode twelve and then increase further. The mean drag per episode for seed zero increases towards the end of the training, while

all other seeds show a decrease in the mean drag. The standard deviation of the mean drag for all seeds is very similar to the simulation DRL training results. Only seed three has an increased standard deviation for about 40 episodes starting from episode 20 and ending at episode 60. After that, it decreases again.

The mean lift coefficient for all seeds deviates larger from the simulation DRL training. In the beginning, the lift stays at a similar level around 0.0 but for all seeds, except for seed one, more or less suddenly decreases around episodes ten to 20. The mean lift for seed one suddenly deviates at episode 50 to 0.7, but slightly decreases afterward towards 0.5. The mean lift coefficient of seed two and five drops to a level of -1.1 at episode 20 and decreases further towards the end of the training. Seed three shows a similar drop, but increases for a short period around episode 40 to -0.6 in order to decrease towards the end to -1.0 . Only seed zero first shows a drop at episode 18 to -0.6 and again at episode 45 to increase again towards the end of the training, reaching -0.49 . The standard deviation of all seeds, except seed three, start at a similar level as the simulation DRL results and are decreasing towards the end of the training reaching 0.01. Seed three has a peak at episode 38 to about 0.31 and shows a more turbulent behavior at higher levels, but decrease also towards the end.

Figure 4.38: Averaged mean angular velocity per episode of the simulation and the five differently seeded model-based DRL trainings using the environment model that has been trained with the weighted MSE loss. Parameter: 5 hidden layers, 256 neurons

Looking at the mean ω_μ in Figure 4.38, it can be seen that the simulation DRL training results are more less stable around $\omega_\mu = 0.0$, while the model-based DRL training results diverge at some point from this level. The seeds zero, two, three and five diverge all early around episode twelve to 20 reaching levels of $\omega_\mu = 2.5$ to $\omega_\mu = 7.5$, and seed 1 yields $\omega_\mu = -5.1$ at minimum. All seeds produce an increasing mean ω_μ towards the end of the training, while seed zero decreases. It is also striking that seed two and five, which showed the most stable mean rewards before, yield a stable ω_μ from episode 20 and 22, respectively. The mean ω_μ increases even further but stays at that magnitude in general. This means that the the most stable and highest rewards are reached, when the angular velocity is almost at the edge of the action space.

Although the mean reward increases, the mean action does not fit the results obtained by the simulation DRL training and therefore, the environment model is not yet sufficient to reflect the physical nature of the flow properly.

The previous elaborations showed that the weighting of the MSE loss function combined with a larger neural network yielded better and more stable results regarding the mean reward per episode than the first model. Although, the actions taken to gain this reward do not reflect the results produced by the simulation DRL training since the average mean action per episode reaches levels towards the edges of the action space. This adds to the conclusion that the influence of the action is not well reflected in the predicted pressure, c_D , and c_L values produced by the chosen model architecture.

Comparison of the Prediction Accuracy

The comparison of the prediction accuracy for the trained models having 50, 128, 256 neurons, as well as for the 256 neuron model trained with the weighted loss function, is depicted in Figure 4.39.

Figure 4.39: Comparison of the MSE and L_{max} prediction error for the tested FFNNs with increased number of neurons and the weighted MSE loss function. The performance has been tested on the whole test set. The y-axis is logarithmically scaled.

The boxplots show the MSE and L_{max} prediction error for the full state, pressure, c_D , and c_L prediction for the different models on the whole test set. The models have each been trained once. The y-axis is scaled logarithmically. It can be seen that the model accuracy increases towards an increasing number of neurons per hidden layer. The 256 neuron model has the lowest prediction error for all different parameters except for the MSE of the pressure prediction. The weighted MSE model has the second-lowest error and is even better regarding pressure prediction. This leads to the conclusion that the prediction error can be further reduced by increasing the number of neurons per hidden layer. Almost tripling the number of neurons from 50 to 128 and then doubling from 128 to 256 led to a decrease of the MSE for the full state of almost a half magnitude and one magnitude, respectively. Therefore increasing the number of neurons further, e.g. 512 or 1024, would decrease the prediction error further and would lead to a sufficient model. Since the 256 neuron model trained with the weighted loss function yields a higher prediction error on the test set the weighted loss function does not necessarily yield better rewards. Only for the

pressure prediction does the weighted loss 256 model yield a lower prediction error regarding the MSE.

4.3.2 Duration of Model-based Trajectory Sampling

Since the ultimate goal of this project is to reduce the DRL training time by using the environment model, the mean prediction time for one trajectory during model-based DRL training, the mean prediction time for ten trajectories, and the time for a single model-based DRL training episode using the 256 neuron model are shown in Table 4.8.

Period	Average Time [s]
Filling buffer using environment model with 10 trajectories	6.3899
Time for a single trajectory	0.6390
Single model-based DRL training episode	8.3282

Table 4.8: Computation times of different periods during model-based DRL training

Since the computation time of a single model-based DRL episode takes on average 8.3282 s, a complete DRL training with 100 episodes using only trajectories generated by the environment model takes on average about 14 min. In comparison, a DRL training run with the same number of episodes using the simulation takes about 4 days.

5. Conclusion

Climate change and the associated shift in society and industry towards sustainable lifestyles put not only aircraft manufacturers under pressure. Improving efficiency and developing technologies to tackle the challenges to come will be one of the main tasks that this generation has to fulfill. Reducing the drag acting on aircraft and vehicles through passive flow control, i.e. constructive measures, is one way to reduce fuel consumption and, therefore, to improve efficiency. Active flow control, which is influencing the flow around an object by inducing external energy into the system, on the other hand, had mostly lacked the ability to find proper control laws, due to the high dimensionality and complexity of most flow control problems. Especially for more complex structures and setups has AFC not yet been able to live up to its full potential. The recent improvements in the field of AI and especially deep reinforcement learning also found their way into the field of fluid mechanics and show promising results for AFC. The 2D flow past a cylinder is, due to its wide application and simple geometry, a good test case for developing and testing AFC using DRL. The flow problem leads, for higher Reynolds numbers to the phenomenon of the von Kármán vortex street, which is responsible for an increasing mean drag and oscillating lift and drag at the cylinder. The DRL agent tries to reduce the drag and mitigate the oscillations by rotating the cylinder having only access to 400 fixed pressure sensors on the cylinder’s surface and a reward signal from the environment. A major drawback of the combination of AFC and DRL is still the long computation time of the CFD simulations that are used to simulate the flow environment around the cylinder. To reduce the computational requirements model-based DRL using another neural network to model the temporal evolution of the cylinder’s surface pressure autoregressively from a previous state to the next state has been applied.

At first, a set of initial trajectories has been generated using the existing DRL setup with the simulation. Although the initial DRL training showed a singular drop at episode 35 the training worked as expected and the trajectories have been rated suitable for the environment model training. Before the data has been used for the environment model training it had to be processed properly. Therefore, the relevant data, containing the pressure, c_D , c_L , and the taken action ω , has been normalized by min-max-scaling to a range between $[-1, 1]$. This step is necessary to remove any dependencies on the data scale for the training of the environment model. Since the environment model has been trained by supervised learning the data has been organized into feature label pairs, corresponding to a previous state and the next state to test against. A fully connected feed-forward neural network has been applied to work as the environment model. It consists of five hidden layers with 50 neurons per layer. The input of the model consists of 400 pressure sensors plus the taken action by the DRL agent of a single time step and the model output is the pressure distribution over the cylinder’s surface for the next time step, as well as the drag and lift coefficients c_D and c_L for the cylinder. The model proved to have a high prediction accuracy for regressively modeling single trajectories, meaning that the model always had access to the true values of the environment. The comparison with the autoregressive prediction of trajectories showed that the chosen approach is not sufficient enough for this task since the prediction error increased by about two to three orders of magnitude. Therefore the model input has been extended using the states of multiple previous time steps to predict the next. Different

numbers of time steps have been tested ranging from one to 30 time steps. Although the results are not always unambiguous since the model architecture might impose higher variance into the training runs due to the lower number of adaptable parameters, the prediction accuracy improved towards higher numbers of time steps. 30 subsequent states have therefore been used for the prediction of the next step. The increased number of time steps has led to an increase in memory consumption. Therefore the influence of the number of pressure sensors used for the model input has been investigated by reducing the number uniformly distributed over the cylinder's surface. The results showed, that fewer numbers of pressure sensors may yield lower prediction errors in general compared to the full pressure information, due to the lower complexity of the neural network. Furthermore, it has been elaborated that the sensor placement, in general, seems to have an influence on the prediction accuracy. Balancing memory consumption and accuracy, 16 pressure sensors per time step have been used for the model input. It has also been shown that the prediction error of the environment model deteriorates the further the model has to autoregressively predict into the future resulting from error accumulation.

Another approach using LSTMs has briefly been applied but the approach has been dropped due to the higher complexity of training, low prediction accuracy, and time constraints.

After the model has been trained the PPO algorithm has been adapted to sample trajectories using only the environment model. The sampled trajectories have been shortened by a factor of 1/2 due to the error accumulation towards later time steps. The first model-based DRL runs have yielded unstable training results because the training diverged, although the resulting rewards have been on average too high in the beginning. The investigation of the source of this behavior has led to the conclusion that the model is not able to predict trajectories yielding higher drag coefficients, therefore producing lower rewards. It has been shown that the chosen environment model architecture has been trained by an imbalanced training set, which has not represented the poorer controlled trajectories of the beginning of the simulation DRL training. Therefore the model has been retrained, although this has not led to a decrease but an increase of the prediction error and the model-based DRL training diverged even more. The investigation of this process led to the conclusion that the action taken by the DRL agent has been underrepresented by the environment model since changing actions yielded similar results regarding the predicted drag and lift coefficient. The architecture has therefore been adjusted by increasing the number of neurons per hidden layer to 128 and 256, and another environment model training using an adapted weighted loss function has been conducted. The larger models showed higher prediction accuracy on the test set and better results regarding the model-based DRL training, although the training still diverged towards later episodes. It has been concluded that the investigated model architectures have also not yet been sufficient to predict the environment properly but extending the size even further might bear sufficient results. Since the overall goal of this thesis is to reduce the time consumption of the DRL training it is important to mention that the time consumption of the model-based DRL learning using only the environment model is about 14 minutes, which is low compared to 4 days required for a simulation-based DRL with a similar setup.

To summarize, the model-based approach presented did not suffice for learning a good control strategy by the DRL agent but it showed the potential of neural networks used for autoregressive time-series prediction within model-based DRL learning. Furthermore, many pitfalls that should be avoided for proper environment modeling have been revealed. It has to be noted that task four has not been conducted due to the challenges encountered with the model-based training using only the environment model and the time constraints of this thesis.

Outlook

The present approach holds great potential for improvements that can be based on this thesis. First of all, a larger FFNN architecture might already be enough to provide proper environment

modeling. Also, proper sensor placement should be investigated because the reduction of pressure sensors together with proper sensor placement might increase the prediction accuracy even further. Since the significance of the action compared to the pressure sensors is small a weighted input for the environment model could be considered. This could be implemented by adapting the fully connected architecture of the model or by just weighting the input, although this would introduce another hyperparameter to be considered that influences the model outcome. The model architecture could also be improved by using a more sophisticated method for hyperparameter optimization for example a grid search or latin hypercube sampling. Since it has been shown that the trajectory data for a DRL training shows different variance regarding the DRL training progress the train and test set split could be adapted to always sample from each episode and not from the whole pool of trajectories. This would avoid or at least reduce the imbalance between the training and test set. Furthermore, to create an initial set of trajectories multiple simulation DRL training runs could be conducted to provide even more data. The variance for the model-based DRL training could also be increased by sampling different start states from an uncontrolled trajectory. Also, the RNN and LSTM approach could be elaborated further since they include temporal dependencies natively in their architecture. Since the model has not been trained autoregressively the model training might improve using an autoregressive training approach. Moving the environment model training from the CPU to the GPU would, furthermore, reduce training time. At last, the environment model training could improve if the model would be trained online during DRL training by repeatedly sampling the first ten trajectories using the simulation and then using these to train the environment model for multiple trajectories and then retraining the model.

Bibliography

- [1] 3Blue1Brown Youtube Channel. Backpropagation calculus | Chapter 4, Deep learning, 2017. Address: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=tIeHLnjs5U8&list=RDCMU CY0_jab_esuFRV4b17AJtAw&start_radio=1, Last access: 02.03.2022.
- [2] James Bergstra, Rémi Bardenet, Yoshua Bengio, and Balázs Kégl. Algorithms for hyperparameter optimization. In J. Shawe-Taylor, R. Zemel, P. Bartlett, F. Pereira, and K. Q. Weinberger, editors, *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, volume 24. Curran Associates, Inc., 2011.
- [3] K. Bieker, S. Peitz, S. L. Brunton, J. N. Kutz, and M. Dellnitz. Deep model predictive flow control with limited sensor data and online learning. *Theoretical and Computational Fluid Dynamics*, 34(4):577–591, 2020.
- [4] C. M. Bishop. *Neural Networks For Pattern Recognition*. Clarendon Press/OUP, 227, 2005.
- [5] Jason Brownlee. Gentle Introduction to the Adam Optimization Algorithm for Deep Learning, 2017. Address: <https://machinelearningmastery.com/adam-optimization-algorithm-for-deep-learning/>, Last access: 02.03.2022.
- [6] Jason Brownlee. How to use Data Scaling Improve Deep Learning Model Stability and Performance. *Machine Learning Mastery*, 2019. Address: <https://machinelearningmastery.com/how-to-improve-neural-network-stability-and-modeling-performance-with-data-scaling/>, Last access: 02.03.2022.
- [7] Anna Choromanska, Mikael Henaff, Michaël Mathieu, Gérard Ben Arous, and Yann LeCun. The loss surface of multilayer networks. *CoRR*, abs/1412.0233, 2014.
- [8] Darshan Thummar. *Active flow control in simulations of fluid flows based on deep reinforcement learning*. Study Thesis, TU Braunschweig, Braunschweig, May, 2021.
- [9] Brian Dean and Bharat Bhushan. Shark-skin surfaces for fluid-drag reduction in turbulent flow: a review. *Philosophical transactions. Series A, Mathematical, physical, and engineering sciences*, 368(1929):4775–4806, 2010.
- [10] R. O. Duda, P. E. Hart, and D. G. Stork. *Pattern Classification*. Wiley, 2nd ed. edition, 2001.
- [11] Thomas Duriez. *Machine Learning Control – Taming Nonlinear Dynamics and Turbulence*, volume 116 of *Springer eBook Collection Engineering*. Springer, Cham, 2017.
- [12] European Union European Commission. Transport Factsheet: Make Transport Greener. 2021. Address: https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/fs_21_3665, Last access: 02.03.2022.
- [13] E. Gabriel, G. E. Fagg, G. Bosilca, T. Angskun, J. J. Dongarra, J. M. Squyres, V. Sahay, P. Kambadur, B. Barrett, A. Lumsdaine, R. H. Castain, D. J. Daniel, R. L. Graham, and T. S. Woodall. Open MPI: Goals, Concept, and Design of a Next Generation MPI

- Implementation. In David Hutchison, Takeo Kanade, Josef Kittler, Jon M. Kleinberg, Friedemann Mattern, John C. Mitchell, Moni Naor, Oscar Nierstrasz, C. Pandu Rangan, Bernhard Steffen, Madhu Sudan, Demetri Terzopoulos, Dough Tygar, Moshe Y. Vardi, Gerhard Weikum, Dieter Kranzlmüller, Péter Kacsuk, and Jack Dongarra, editors, *Recent Advances in Parallel Virtual Machine and Message Passing Interface*, volume 3241 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, pages 97–104. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2004.
- [14] F. Gabriel. *Aktive Regelung einer Zylinderumströmung bei variierender Reynoldszahl durch bestärkendes Lernen*. Bachelor Thesis, TU Braunschweig, Braunschweig, October, 2021.
- [15] Paul Garnier, Jonathan Viquerat, Jean Rabault, Aurélien Larcher, Alexander Kuhnle, and Elie Hachem. A review on deep reinforcement learning for fluid mechanics. *Computers & Fluids*, 225:104973, 2021.
- [16] H. Ghraieb, J. Viquerat, A. Larcher, P. Meliga, and E. Hachem. Single-step deep reinforcement learning for open-loop control of laminar and turbulent flows. *Physical Review Fluids*, 6(5), 2021.
- [17] I. Goodfellow, Y. Bengio, and A. Courville. *Deep Learning*. MIT Press, 2016.
- [18] R. H. R. Hahnloser, R. Sarpeshkar, M. A. Mahowald, R. J. Douglas, and S. Seung. Digital selection and analogue ampli@cation coexist in a cortex-inspired silicon circuit. *Nature*, (Vol. 405), 2000.
- [19] Sepp Hochreiter and Jürgen Schmidhuber. Long Short-term Memory. *Neural computation*, 9:1735–1780, 1997.
- [20] F. Hutter, L. Kotthoff, and J. Vanschoren. *Automated Machine Learning*. Springer International Publishing, Cham, 2019.
- [21] Facebook Inc. PyTorch Website, 2022. Address: <https://pytorch.org/features/>, Last access: 02.03.2022.
- [22] G. James, D. Witten, T. Hastie, and R. Tibshirani. *An Introduction to Statistical Learning*. Springer US, New York, NY, 2021.
- [23] James Bergstra and Yoshua Bengio. Random Search for Hyper-Parameter Optimization. *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, 13(10):281–305, 2012.
- [24] Katarzyna Janocha and Wojciech Marian Czarnecki. On loss functions for deep neural networks in classification. *CoRR*, abs/1702.05659, 2017.
- [25] Hrvoje Jasak. OpenFOAM: open source CFD in research and industry. *International Journal of Naval Architecture and Ocean Engineering*, 1:89–94, 2009.
- [26] Lukasz Kaiser, Mohammad Babaeizadeh, Piotr Milos, Blazej Osinski, Roy H. Campbell, Konrad Czechowski, Dumitru Erhan, Chelsea Finn, Piotr Kozakowski, Sergey Levine, Afroz Mohiuddin, Ryan Sepassi, George Tucker, and Henryk Michalewski. Model-Based Reinforcement Learning for Atari.
- [27] D. P. Kingma and J. Ba. Adam: A Method for Stochastic Optimization. *arXiv*, 1412.6980v9, 2014.
- [28] A. Lenail. NN SVG Website: Publication-ready NN-architecture schematics., 2021. Address: <http://alexlenail.me/NN-SVG/index.html>, Last access: 02.03.2022.
- [29] M. Morales. *grokking Deep Reinforcement Learning*. Manning Publications Co., 2020.
- [30] M. Nielsen. *Neural Networks and Deep Learning*. Determination Press, 2015.

- [31] C. Olah. Understanding LSTM Networks: colah’s blog, 2015. Address: <https://colah.github.io/posts/2015-08-Understanding-LSTMs/>, Last access: 02.03.2022.
- [32] OpenCFD Ltd. OpenFOAM Website, 2022. Address: <https://www.openfoam.com/>, Last access: 02.03.2022.
- [33] Romain Paris, Samir Beneddine, and Julien Dandois. Robust flow control and optimal sensor placement using deep reinforcement learning. *Journal of Fluid Mechanics*, 913, 2021.
- [34] Razvan Pascanu, Tomas Mikolov, and Yoshua Bengio. On the difficulty of training recurrent neural networks. In Sanjoy Dasgupta and David McAllester, editors, *Proceedings of the 30th International Conference on Machine Learning*, volume 28 of *Proceedings of Machine Learning Research*, pages 1310–1318, Atlanta, Georgia, USA, 2013. PMLR.
- [35] Adam Paszke, Sam Gross, Francisco Massa, Adam Lerer, James Bradbury, Gregory Chanan, Trevor Killeen, Zeming Lin, Natalia Gimelshein, Luca Antiga, Alban Desmaison, Andreas Kopf, Edward Yang, Zachary DeVito, Martin Raison, Alykhan Tejani, Sasank Chilamkurthy, Benoit Steiner, Lu Fang, Junjie Bai, and Soumith Chintala. PyTorch: An Imperative Style, High-Performance Deep Learning Library. In H. Wallach, H. Larochelle, A. Beygelzimer, F. d\textquotesingle Alché-Buc, E. Fox, and R. Garnett, editors, *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems 32*, pages 8024–8035. Curran Associates, Inc, 2019.
- [36] Po-Wei Chou, Daniel Maturana, and Sebastian Scherer. Improving Stochastic Policy Gradients in Continuous Control with Deep Reinforcement Learning using the Beta Distribution. In Doina Precup and Yee Whye Teh, editors, *Proceedings of the 34th International Conference on Machine Learning*, volume 70 of *Proceedings of Machine Learning Research*, pages 834–843. PMLR, 2017.
- [37] Joshua L. Proctor, Steven L. Brunton, and J. Nathan Kutz. Dynamic Mode Decomposition with Control. *SIAM Journal on Applied Dynamical Systems*, 15(1):142–161, 2016.
- [38] Sheng Qin, Shuyue Wang, Jean Rabault, and Gang Sun. An application of data driven reward of deep reinforcement learning by dynamic mode decomposition in active flow control. 2021.
- [39] Jean Rabault, Miroslav Kuchta, Atle Jensen, Ulysse Réglade, and Nicolas Cerardi. Artificial neural networks trained through deep reinforcement learning discover control strategies for active flow control. *Journal of Fluid Mechanics*, 865:281–302, 2019.
- [40] Jean Rabault and Alexander Kuhnle. Accelerating deep reinforcement learning strategies of flow control through a multi-environment approach. *Physics of Fluids*, 31(9):094105, 2019.
- [41] M. Raissi, P. Perdikaris, and G. E. Karniadakis. Physics-informed neural networks: A deep learning framework for solving forward and inverse problems involving nonlinear partial differential equations. *Journal of Computational Physics*, 378:686–707, 2019.
- [42] S. Robertson. NLP From Scratch: Translation with a Sequence to Sequence Network and Attention: PyTorch Tutorials 1.10.1+cu102 documentation, 2022. Address: https://pytorch.org/tutorials/intermediate/seq2seq_translation_tutorial.html, Last access: 02.03.2022.
- [43] M. Schäfer, S. Turek, F. Durst, E. Krause, and R. Rannacher. Benchmark Computations of Laminar Flow Around a Cylinder. In Ernst Heinrich Hirschel, editor, *Flow Simulation with High-Performance Computers II*, volume 48 of *Notes on Numerical Fluid Mechanics (NNFM)*, pages 547–566. Vieweg+Teubner Verlag, Wiesbaden, 1996.
- [44] Peter J. Schmid. Dynamic mode decomposition of numerical and experimental data. *Journal of Fluid Mechanics*, 656:5–28, 2010.

-
- [45] Shahab Shahinfar, Sohrab S. Sattarzadeh, Jens H. M. Fransson, and Alessandro Talamelli. Revival of Classical Vortex Generators Now for Transition Delay. *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, 109(7):074501, 2012.
- [46] Eli Stevens, Luca Antiga, and Thomas Viehmann. *Deep learning with PyTorch*. Manning Publications Co, Shelter Island NY, 2020.
- [47] Yuwen Sun, Xin Yuan, Wenzhang Liu, and Changyin Sun. Model-Based Reinforcement Learning via Proximal Policy Optimization. *Proceedings 2019 Chinese Automation Congress (CAC2019)*, pages 4736–4740, 2019.
- [48] Richard S. Sutton and Andrew G. Barto. *Reinforcement learning: An introduction*. Adaptive computation and machine learning series. The MIT Press, Cambridge Massachusetts, second edition edition, 2018.
- [49] Sylabs, Inc. Introduction to Singularity — Singularity container 3.6 documentation, 2021. Address: <https://sylabs.io/guides/3.6/user-guide/introduction.html>, Last access: 02.03.2022.
- [50] Hongwei Tang, Jean Rabault, Alexander Kuhnle, Yan Wang, and Tongguang Wang. Robust active flow control over a range of Reynolds numbers using an artificial neural network trained through deep reinforcement learning. *Physics of Fluids*, 32(5):053605, 2020.
- [51] Technische Universität. Phoenix HPC Cluster Website, 2022. Address: <https://www.tu-braunschweig.de/it/dienste/21/phoenix>, Last access: 02.03.2022.
- [52] The Open MPI Project. OpenMPI Website: FAQ: General information about the Open MPI Project, 2022. Address: <https://www-1b.open-mpi.org/faq/?category=general>, Last Access: 02.03.2022.
- [53] Mikhail Tokarev, Egor Palkin, and Rustam Mullyadzhanov. Deep Reinforcement Learning Control of Cylinder Flow Using Rotary Oscillations at Low Reynolds Number. *Energies*, 13(22):5920, 2020.
- [54] Jie Wang. An Intuitive Tutorial to Gaussian Processes Regression. *arXiv*, 2009.10862, 2021.
- [55] A. Weiner. Personal Communication. 2021/2022.
- [56] Wikimedia User:Ixnay. Recurrent neural network, 2022. Address: https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Recurrent_neural_network&oldid=1071560716, Last access: 02.03.2022.
- [57] C. H. K. Williamson. Vortex Dynamics in the Cylinder Wake. *Annual Review of Fluid Mechanics*, 28(1):477–539, 1996.
- [58] Xue Ying. An Overview of Overfitting and its Solutions. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1168:022022, 2019.

List of Figures

1.1	Comparison of the velocity field of the uncontrolled (a) and actively controlled (b) flow of a 2D cylinder flow	2
1.2	Structure of the MPC control scheme by Bieker et al. [3]; Image source: Figure 1 from [3]	3
2.1	Velocity magnitude of a simulated 2D flow past a cylinder in a channel at $Re = 50$	5
2.2	Photographs of vortex street visualization	6
2.4	Example of a fully connected deep feedforward neural network with 2 hidden layers	7
2.5	Rectified linear unit activation function	8
2.6	Performance of the Adam optimizer in comparison to other methods	9
2.7	Example of the structure of a recurrent neural network. The unfolded network is depicted on the right side	10
2.8	Example of the structure of an LSTM recurrent neural network.	10
3.1	Geometry of the simulation environment	11
3.2	Example mesh with $N_x = 275$ and $N_y = 50$	13
3.3	Agent-environment interaction	15
3.4	Flowchart of the PPO algorithm.	17
3.5	Reduced depiction of initial feedforward neural network structure.	20
4.1	Comparison of the rewards obtained by the initial DRL training conducted for this thesis and the findings of [14].	22
4.2	Means and standard deviations of different parameters of the initial DRL training per episode averaged over all trajectories of each episode.	23
4.3	c_D , c_L in-sample prediction (red, orange) and real (black, blue) values over the course of four unseen trajectories.	25
4.4	In-sample relative prediction error for all 400 pressure sensors over the course of four different trajectories.	25
4.5	c_D , c_L autoregressive prediction (red, orange) and real (black, blue) values over the course of four unseen trajectories.	27
4.6	Autoregressive relative prediction error for all 400 pressure sensors over the course of four unssen trajectories.	27
4.7	Comparison between MSE and L_{max} of models with different subsequent states.	28
4.8	Comparison between MSE and L_{max} of models with different numbers of pressure sensors as input for the environment model.	30
4.9	Autoregressive predicted and real c_D and c_L coefficients per step of four different random trajectories.	32
4.10	Heatmaps of the relative autoregressive prediction error per sensor of four different random trajectories.	32
4.11	MSE and L_{max} prediction error per step of four different random trajectories.	33
4.12	(a) c_D , c_L prediction (orange) and real (blue) values over the course of a single trajectory. (b) Relative prediction error for all 400 pressure sensors over the course of a single trajectory.	34
4.13	(a) c_D , c_L prediction (orange) and real (blue) values over the course of a single trajectory. (b) Relative prediction error for all 400 pressure sensors over the course of a single trajectory.	34
4.14	Exemplary training and validation loss of a tested multi-layer LSTM.	36
4.15	Predicted and real c_D and c_L plotted for five different test trajectories of a tested multi-layer LSTM.	36

4.16	Flow chart of model-based trajectory sampling and filling of the replay buffer. . .	38
4.17	Mean reward and standard deviation per episode of 11 differently seeded model-based DRL trainings in comparison to the reward of the initial DRL training conducted with the simulation. Parameters: 50 neurons, 5 layers	40
4.18	Mean drag coefficient and standard deviation per episode of 11 differently seeded model-based DRL trainings in comparison to the reward of the initial DRL training conducted with the simulation. Parameters: 50 neurons, 5 layers	40
4.19	Mean lift coefficient and standard deviation per episode of eleven differently seeded model-based DRL trainings in comparison to the reward of the initial DRL training conducted with the simulation. Parameters: 50 neurons, 5 layers	41
4.20	Average mean angular velocity and standard deviation per episode of 11 differently seeded model-based DRL trainings in comparison to the reward of the initial DRL training conducted with the simulation. Parameters: 50 neurons, 5 layers	41
4.21	MSE and MAE of autoregressive trajectory predictions tested per episode of the initial simulation DRL training.	42
4.22	MSE and MAE of autoregressive trajectory predictions of the retrained environment model, tested per episode of the initial simulation DRL training.	43
4.23	MSE and MAE of autoregressive pressure predictions per trajectory of the pre-trained and retrained environment model, tested per episode of the initial simulation DRL training.	43
4.24	ω_μ , c_D , c_L and reward for the predicted time steps of episode 1 of a model-based DRL training using the retrained model. The dashed red line marks the start of the prediction. Parameters: 50 neurons, 5 layers	44
4.25	ω_μ , c_D , c_L and reward for the predicted time steps of episode 8 of a model-based DRL training using the retrained model. The dashed red line marks the start of the prediction. Parameters: 50 neurons, 5 layers	45
4.26	ω_μ , c_D , c_L and reward for the predicted time steps of episode 45 of a model-based DRL training using the retrained model. The dashed red line marks the start of the prediction. Parameters: 50 neurons, 5 layers	45
4.27	c_D and c_L of the uncontrolled flow.	47
4.28	ω_μ , c_D , c_L and reward for the predicted time steps of episode 1 of a model-based DRL training using always the same start state from the uncontrolled flow and dropping trajectories yielding a mean reward < -0.5 . The dashed red line marks the start of the prediction. Parameters: 50 neurons, 5 layers	47
4.29	ω_μ , c_D , c_L and reward for the predicted time steps of episode 8 of a model-based DRL training using always the same start state from the uncontrolled flow and dropping trajectories yielding a mean reward < -0.5 . The dashed red line marks the start of the prediction. Parameters: 50 neurons, 5 layers	48
4.30	ω_μ , c_D , c_L and reward for the predicted time steps of episode 36 of a model-based DRL training using always the same start state from the uncontrolled flow and dropping trajectories yielding a mean reward < -0.5 . The dashed red line marks the start of the prediction. Parameters: 50 neurons, 5 layers	48
4.31	Mean reward per episode of the simulation and the model-based DRL training for the 128 and 256 neuron environment models.	50
4.32	Mean drag per episode of the simulation and the model-based DRL training for the 128 and 256 neuron environment models.	50
4.33	Mean lift per episode of the simulation and the model-based DRL training for the 128 and 256 neuron environment models.	51
4.34	Mean omega mean per episode of the simulation and the model-based DRL training for the 128 and 256 neuron environment models.	51
4.35	Mean reward per episode of the simulation and five differently seeded model-based DRL trainings using the environment model that has been trained with the weighted MSE loss. Parameter: 5 hidden layers, 256 neurons	53
4.36	Mean drag coefficient per episode of the simulation and the five differently seeded model-based DRL trainings using the environment model that has been trained with the weighted MSE loss. Parameter: 5 hidden layers, 256 neurons	53
4.37	Mean lift coefficient per episode of the simulation and the five differently seeded model-based DRL trainings using the environment model that has been trained with the weighted MSE loss. Parameter: 5 hidden layers, 256 neurons	54

4.38	Averaged mean angular velocity per episode of the simulation and the five differently seeded model-based DRL trainings using the environment model that has been trained with the weighted MSE loss. Parameter: 5 hidden layers, 256 neurons	55
4.39	Comparison of the MSE and L_{max} prediction error for the tested FFNNs with increased number of neurons and the weighted MSE loss function. The performance has been tested on the whole test set. The y-axis is logarithmically scaled.	56
A.1	(a) c_D , c_L prediction and real values over the course of a single trajectory. (b) Relative prediction error for all 400 pressure sensors over the course of a single trajectory. The colours from blue to yellow indicates the size of the relative prediction error per sensor. Parameters: 128 neurons, 2 hidden layers.	xxiv
A.2	(a) c_D , c_L prediction and real values over the course of a single trajectory. (b) Relative prediction error for all 400 pressure sensors over the course of a single trajectory. The colours from blue to yellow indicates the size of the relative prediction error per sensor. Parameters: 128 neurons, 3 hidden layers.	xxiv
A.3	(a) c_D , c_L prediction and real values over the course of a single trajectory. (b) Relative prediction error for all 400 pressure sensors over the course of a single trajectory. The colours from blue to yellow indicates the size of the relative prediction error per sensor. Parameters: 128 neurons, 4 hidden layers.	xxv
B.1	c_D and c_L predictions and real values of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 10, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 64.	xxvii
B.2	Relative pressure error per sensor of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 10, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 64.	xxvii
B.3	Train and validation loss of multi-step LSTM training. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 10, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 64.	xxviii
B.4	c_D and c_L predictions and real values of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 20, prediction sequence length = 10, batch size = 64.	xxviii
B.5	Relative pressure error per sensor of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 20, prediction sequence length = 10, batch size = 64.	xxix
B.6	Train and validation loss of multi-step LSTM training. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 20, prediction sequence length = 10, batch size = 64.	xxix
B.7	c_D and c_L predictions and real values of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 20, prediction sequence length = 20, batch size = 64.	xxx
B.8	Relative pressure error per sensor of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 20, prediction sequence length = 20, batch size = 64.	xxx
B.9	Train and validation loss of multi-step LSTM training. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 20, prediction sequence length = 20, batch size = 64.	xxxii
B.10	c_D and c_L predictions and real values of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 20, prediction sequence length = 30, batch size = 64.	xxxii
B.11	Relative pressure error per sensor of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 20, prediction sequence length = 30, batch size = 64.	xxxii
B.12	Train and validation loss of multi-step LSTM training. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 20, prediction sequence length = 30, batch size = 64.	xxxii
B.13	c_D and c_L predictions and real values of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 30, prediction sequence length = 30, batch size = 64.	xxxiii

B.14	Relative pressure error per sensor of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 30, prediction sequence length = 30, batch size = 64.	xxxiii
B.15	Train and validation loss of multi-step LSTM training. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 30, prediction sequence length = 30, batch size = 64.	xxxiv
B.16	c_D and c_L predictions and real values of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 30, prediction sequence length = 20, batch size = 64.	xxxiv
B.17	Relative pressure error per sensor of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 30, prediction sequence length = 20, batch size = 64.	xxxv
B.18	Train and validation loss of multi-step LSTM training. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 30, prediction sequence length = 20, batch size = 64.	xxxv
B.19	c_D and c_L predictions and real values of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 30, prediction sequence length = 30, batch size = 64.	xxxvi
B.20	Relative pressure error per sensor of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 30, prediction sequence length = 30, batch size = 64.	xxxvi
B.21	Train and validation loss of multi-step LSTM training. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 30, prediction sequence length = 30, batch size = 64.	xxxvii
B.22	c_D and c_L predictions and real values of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 40, prediction sequence length = 10, batch size = 64.	xxxvii
B.23	Relative pressure error per sensor of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 40, prediction sequence length = 10, batch size = 64.	xxxviii
B.24	Train and validation loss of multi-step LSTM training. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 40, prediction sequence length = 10, batch size = 64.	xxxviii
B.25	c_D and c_L predictions and real values of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 40, prediction sequence length = 20, batch size = 64.	xxxix
B.26	Relative pressure error per sensor of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 40, prediction sequence length = 20, batch size = 64.	xxxix
B.27	Train and validation loss of multi-step LSTM training. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 40, prediction sequence length = 20, batch size = 64.	xl
B.28	c_D and c_L predictions and real values of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 10, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 128.	xl
B.29	Relative pressure error per sensor of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 10, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 128.	xli
B.30	Train and validation loss of multi-step LSTM training. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 10, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 128.	xli
B.31	c_D and c_L predictions and real values of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 10, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 256.	xlii
B.32	Relative pressure error per sensor of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 10, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 256.	xlii
B.33	Train and validation loss of multi-step LSTM training. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 10, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 256.	xliii

B.34	c_D and c_L predictions and real values of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 20, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 256.	xliii
B.35	Relative pressure error per sensor of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 20, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 256.	xliv
B.36	Train and validation loss of multi-step LSTM training. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 20, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 256.	xliv
B.37	c_D and c_L predictions and real values of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 30, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 256.	xlv
B.38	Relative pressure error per sensor of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 30, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 256.	xlv
B.39	Train and validation loss of multi-step LSTM training. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 30, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 256.	xlvi
B.40	c_D and c_L predictions and real values of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 40, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 256.	xlvi
B.41	Relative pressure error per sensor of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter:	xlvii
B.42	Train and validation loss of multi-step LSTM training. Parameter:	xlvii
B.43	c_D and c_L predictions and real values of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 50, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 256.	xlviii
B.44	Relative pressure error per sensor of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 50, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 256.	xlviii
B.45	Train and validation loss of multi-step LSTM training. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 50, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 256.	xlix
B.46	c_D and c_L predictions and real values of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 10, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 512	xlix
B.47	Relative pressure error per sensor of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 10, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 512	l
B.48	Train and validation loss of multi-step LSTM training. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 10, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 512	l
B.49	c_D and c_L predictions and real values of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 2 layers, feature sequence length = 10, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 256.	li
B.50	Relative pressure error per sensor of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 2 layer, feature sequence length = 10, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 256.	li
B.51	Train and validation loss of multi-step LSTM training. Parameter: 50 neurons, 2 layer, feature sequence length = 10, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 256.	lii
B.52	c_D and c_L predictions and real values of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 3 layers, feature sequence length = 10, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 256.	lii
B.53	Relative pressure error per sensor of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 3 layers, feature sequence length = 10, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 256.	liii
B.54	Train and validation loss of multi-step LSTM training. Parameter: 50 neurons, 3 layers, feature sequence length = 10, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 256.	liii

B.55 c_D and c_L predictions and real values of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 4 layers, feature sequence length = 10, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 256.	liv
B.56 Relative pressure error per sensor of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 4 layers, feature sequence length = 10, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 256.	liv
B.57 Train and validation loss of multi-step LSTM training. Parameter: 50 neurons, 4 layers, feature sequence length = 10, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 256.	lv
B.58 c_D and c_L predictions and real values of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 5 layers, feature sequence length = 10, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 256.	lv
B.59 Relative pressure error per sensor of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 5 layers, feature sequence length = 10, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 256.	lvi
B.60 Train and validation loss of multi-step LSTM training. Parameter: 50 neurons, 5 layers, feature sequence length = 10, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 256.	lvi

List of Tables

4.1	In-sample mean and maximum mean squared and mean absolute errors over full test set.	24
4.2	Autoregressive mean, standard deviation and maximum mean squared and mean absolute errors over full test set.	26
4.3	Medians of MSE and maximum error of full state, pressure, c_D and c_L prediction for models with different numbers of subsequent input steps. The data has been generated using the full test set.	28
4.4	Single and double precision memory consumption of the different numbers of pressure sensors in comparison.	29
4.5	Medians of MSE and maximum error of full state, pressure, c_D and c_L prediction for models with different numbers of pressure sensors used for model input. The data has been generated using the full test set.	30
4.6	Different parameter combinations of hyperparameters used for multi-step LSTM .	35
4.7	Parameters of the first model-based DRL training using only the environment model.	37
4.8	Computation times of different periods during model-based DRL training	57

A. Results Single-Step LSTM

Figure A.1: (a) c_D , c_L prediction and real values over the course of a single trajectory. (b) Relative prediction error for all 400 pressure sensors over the course of a single trajectory. The colours from blue to yellow indicates the size of the relative prediction error per sensor. Parameters: 128 neurons, 2 hidden layers.

Figure A.2: (a) c_D , c_L prediction and real values over the course of a single trajectory. (b) Relative prediction error for all 400 pressure sensors over the course of a single trajectory. The colours from blue to yellow indicates the size of the relative prediction error per sensor. Parameters: 128 neurons, 3 hidden layers.

Figure A.3: (a) c_D , c_L prediction and real values over the course of a single trajectory. (b) Relative prediction error for all 400 pressure sensors over the course of a single trajectory. The colours from blue to yellow indicates the size of the relative prediction error per sensor. Parameters: 128 neurons, 4 hidden layers.

B. Results Multi-Step LSTM

Figure B.1: c_D and c_L predictions and real values of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 10, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 64.

Figure B.2: Relative pressure error per sensor of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 10, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 64.

Figure B.3: Train and validation loss of multi-step LSTM training. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 10, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 64.

Figure B.4: c_D and c_L predictions and real values of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 20, prediction sequence length = 10, batch size = 64.

Figure B.5: Relative pressure error per sensor of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 20, prediction sequence length = 10, batch size = 64.

Figure B.6: Train and validation loss of multi-step LSTM training. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 20, prediction sequence length = 10, batch size = 64.

Figure B.7: c_D and c_L predictions and real values of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 20, prediction sequence length = 20, batch size = 64.

Figure B.8: Relative pressure error per sensor of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 20, prediction sequence length = 20, batch size = 64.

Figure B.9: Train and validation loss of multi-step LSTM training. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 20, prediction sequence length = 20, batch size = 64.

Figure B.10: c_D and c_L predictions and real values of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 20, prediction sequence length = 30, batch size = 64.

Figure B.11: Relative pressure error per sensor of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 20, prediction sequence length = 30, batch size = 64.

Figure B.12: Train and validation loss of multi-step LSTM training. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 20, prediction sequence length = 30, batch size = 64.

Figure B.13: c_D and c_L predictions and real values of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 30, prediction sequence length = 30, batch size = 64.

Figure B.14: Relative pressure error per sensor of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 30, prediction sequence length = 30, batch size = 64.

Figure B.15: Train and validation loss of multi-step LSTM training. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 30, prediction sequence length = 30, batch size = 64.

Figure B.16: c_D and c_L predictions and real values of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 30, prediction sequence length = 20, batch size = 64.

Figure B.17: Relative pressure error per sensor of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 30, prediction sequence length = 20, batch size = 64.

Figure B.18: Train and validation loss of multi-step LSTM training. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 30, prediction sequence length = 20, batch size = 64.

Figure B.19: c_D and c_L predictions and real values of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer1, feature sequence length = 30, prediction sequence length = 30, batch size = 64.

Figure B.20: Relative pressure error per sensor of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer1, feature sequence length = 30, prediction sequence length = 30, batch size = 64.

Figure B.21: Train and validation loss of multi-step LSTM training. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 30, prediction sequence length = 30, batch size = 64.

Figure B.22: c_D and c_L predictions and real values of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 40, prediction sequence length = 10, batch size = 64.

Figure B.23: Relative pressure error per sensor of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 40, prediction sequence length = 10, batch size = 64.

Figure B.24: Train and validation loss of multi-step LSTM training. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 40, prediction sequence length = 10, batch size = 64.

Figure B.25: c_D and c_L predictions and real values of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 40, prediction sequence length = 20, batch size = 64.

Figure B.26: Relative pressure error per sensor of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 40, prediction sequence length = 20, batch size = 64.

Figure B.27: Train and validation loss of multi-step LSTM training. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 40, prediction sequence length = 20, batch size = 64.

Figure B.28: c_D and c_L predictions and real values of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 10, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 128.

Figure B.29: Relative pressure error per sensor of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 10, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 128.

Figure B.30: Train and validation loss of multi-step LSTM training. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 10, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 128.

Figure B.31: c_D and c_L predictions and real values of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 10, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 256.

Figure B.32: Relative pressure error per sensor of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 10, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 256.

Figure B.33: Train and validation loss of multi-step LSTM training. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 10, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 256.

Figure B.34: c_D and c_L predictions and real values of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 20, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 256.

Figure B.35: Relative pressure error per sensor of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 20, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 256.

Figure B.36: Train and validation loss of multi-step LSTM training. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 20, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 256.

Figure B.37: c_D and c_L predictions and real values of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 30, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 256.

Figure B.38: Relative pressure error per sensor of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 30, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 256.

Figure B.39: Train and validation loss of multi-step LSTM training. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 30, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 256.

Figure B.40: c_D and c_L predictions and real values of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 40, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 256.

Figure B.41: Relative pressure error per sensor of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter:

Figure B.42: Train and validation loss of multi-step LSTM training. Parameter:

Figure B.43: c_D and c_L predictions and real values of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 50, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 256.

Figure B.44: Relative pressure error per sensor of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 50, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 256.

Figure B.45: Train and validation loss of multi-step LSTM training. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 50, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 256.

Figure B.46: c_D and c_L predictions and real values of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 10, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 512

Figure B.47: Relative pressure error per sensor of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 10, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 512

Figure B.48: Train and validation loss of multi-step LSTM training. Parameter: 50 neurons, 1 layer, feature sequence length = 10, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 512

Figure B.49: c_D and c_L predictions and real values of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 2 layers, feature sequence length = 10, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 256.

Figure B.50: Relative pressure error per sensor of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 2 layer, feature sequence length = 10, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 256.

Figure B.51: Train and validation loss of multi-step LSTM training. Parameter: 50 neurons, 2 layer, feature sequence length = 10, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 256.

Figure B.52: c_D and c_L predictions and real values of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 3 layers, feature sequence length = 10, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 256.

Figure B.53: Relative pressure error per sensor of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 3 layers, feature sequence length = 10, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 256.

Figure B.54: Train and validation loss of multi-step LSTM training. Parameter: 50 neurons, 3 layers, feature sequence length = 10, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 256.

Figure B.55: c_D and c_L predictions and real values of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 4 layers, feature sequence length = 10, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 256.

Figure B.56: Relative pressure error per sensor of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 4 layers, feature sequence length = 10, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 256.

Figure B.57: Train and validation loss of multi-step LSTM training. Parameter: 50 neurons, 4 layers, feature sequence length = 10, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 256.

Figure B.58: c_D and c_L predictions and real values of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 5 layers, feature sequence length = 10, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 256.

Figure B.59: Relative pressure error per sensor of multi-step LSTM for five different trajectories. Parameter: 50 neurons, 5 layers, feature sequence length = 10, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 256.

Figure B.60: Train and validation loss of multi-step LSTM training. Parameter: 50 neurons, 5 layers, feature sequence length = 10, prediction sequence length = 5, batch size = 256.